

UNIVERSITY OF PERUGIA
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

PhD Programme in Physics
V Cycle – 1990/91/92

Quantum Systems in Dissipative Environments

Candidate:
Marco Patriarca

Supervisor:
Prof. Pasquale Sodano
Co-supervisor:
Prof. Fabio Marchesoni

Thesis submitted for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy
Academic Year 1992/1993

Final examination

Date of defence: **30 September 1993**

Venue: Ministry of University and Scientific and Technological Research,
Viale Trastevere, Rome

National Examining Board

Prof. Riccardo Barbieri	University of Pisa
Prof. Antonino Sciarrino	University of Naples
Prof. Francesco Saverio Persico	University of Palermo

Referees

Prof. Yogi Srivastava	University of Perugia (internal)
Prof. Silvio De Siena	University of Salerno (external)

Acknowledgements

The completion of this work has benefited from the valued and essential contributions of many people. In particular I would like to thank:

Roberto Onofrio, University of Padua, and Fabio Marchesoni, University of Camerino, who brought to my attention and sparked my interest in mesoscopic systems and the Feynman–Vernon model;

Silvio De Siena, University of Salerno, for his clear seminars on the oscillator model and quantum Brownian motion, as well as for his excellent advice on the writing of the thesis;

the people with whom I have collaborated, in particular Enzo Barone, University of Perugia, and Fabrizio Illuminati, University of Padua, also for useful conversations;

Carlo Lucheroni and Grazia Pula, University of Perugia, for fruitful discussions on the problem of quantum delocalisation of bodies;

Pasquale Sodano, University of Perugia, for the prolific collaboration from which many of the ideas around which the thesis was developed were born, in particular regarding the problem of a particle in a magnetic field, and for having followed with patience and interest the development of some particularly difficult phases of the work.

Abstract

The present work is devoted to the study of the Feynman–Vernon model, an exactly solvable mechanical model for the description of dissipative quantum systems, in which a central degree of freedom interacts with an infinite set of harmonic oscillators with an arbitrary frequency distribution.

In the first part of the work the general properties of the model are studied. In particular, it is shown how the presence of initial correlations between the central system and the dissipative environment is unavoidable for reasons of translational invariance, and how neglecting them leads to physically incorrect results, including the violation of Ehrenfest’s theorem for the motion of the centre of mass of a wave packet.

In the second part the results are applied to several physical situations: the problem of quantum delocalisation of a macroscopic body interacting with a dissipative environment, the motion of a particle in an external electric field both in the absence and in the presence of coupling between the environment and the field, and finally the two-dimensional motion of a charged particle in a magnetic field in a dissipative environment.

Contents

Acknowledgements	2
Abstract	3
Introduction	5
I Theory	10
1 Classical model	11
2 Quantum model	25
3 Free particle	35
II Applications	40
4 Quantum delocalisation of a body interacting with the environment	41
5 Particle in an electric field	50
6 Particle in a magnetic field	57
A Calculation of the influence functional	70
B Effective propagator for the free particle	73
C Probability functional for Gaussian processes	77
Chronological Bibliography	79
Publications related to the thesis	82

Introduction

Within classical physics, even though a description of dissipative phenomena based on the principle of least action is not possible [51], a phenomenological description can still be achieved through random trajectories defined by stochastic differential equations [41] (such as the Langevin equation [42]) or through functions representing probability densities satisfying particular continuous or discrete equations (such as the Fokker–Planck equations [46], the Boltzmann equation [32] or the “master equations” [44]).

In other words, instead of starting from the study of a Lagrangian associated with a microscopic model of a dissipative system, one uses quantities that already contain within their definitions the required statistical properties. The search for a classical mechanical model for dissipative phenomena therefore remains, at least from a more pragmatic standpoint, only a matter of principle.

The classical approximation is, however, no longer adequate as soon as quantum fluctuations become comparable to statistical ones, i.e. when $\hbar\omega \simeq kT$, where T is the absolute temperature and $1/\omega \simeq \tau$ is the characteristic time of the classical system, which can be determined for example by its relaxation time or by the natural frequency with which the system oscillates around its equilibrium position [47].

When one undertakes the study of the quantum mechanics of a dissipative system, the situation encountered is substantially different.

A quantum description is, at first sight, nonsensical, since for dissipative systems a Hamiltonian is not definable [51] and it is therefore impossible to write the corresponding Schrödinger equation.

The path to quantisation of a system passes, according to conventional procedures, through knowledge of its microscopic dynamics – the Hamiltonian if one uses the canonical quantisation procedure, or the Lagrangian if one uses the functional formulation of quantum mechanics. For a dissipative system neither can be defined. The reason is that the problem of a degree of freedom interacting with a dissipative environment is in fact a many-body problem – indeed a problem with infinitely many degrees of freedom.

The description of a subsystem interacting with a generic “environment” – a dissipative one in the present case – is possible at most, according to the principles of quantum mechanics, through a density matrix, but certainly not through a wave function [45].

Applying canonical quantisation directly to the variables of the system under study, while neglecting the environmental variables, amounts to assuming the existence of a description in terms of a wave function and can indeed lead to difficulties of various kinds (see [13] for an overview of the subject).

In this context, a model consisting of the degrees of freedom of a “central particle” together with the infinitely many degrees of freedom of the “environment” stands as the natural candidate for a mechanical model of a dissipative system.

To fix ideas, reference will often be made to the example of a particle diffusing in a fluid. In this case the degrees of freedom of the “central particle” are its translational degrees of freedom, while the degrees of freedom of the “environment” are those modelling the dynamics of the interaction with the molecules of the fluid.

Whether studied from a classical or a quantum standpoint, the problem of an infinite number of mutually coupled degrees of freedom is exactly solvable only when the Lagrangian of the total system is quadratic in the coordinates. This is precisely the infinite harmonic-oscillator thermal bath model, which is the subject of the present work.

Examples of environments represented by harmonic oscillator models can already be found in classical electrodynamics [26] and in the important applications of quantum electrodynamics [28].

It is no accident that the work of I.R. Senitzky [1, 5] on a particle interacting with the electromagnetic radiation of a cavity suggested an analogy between a particle in an electromagnetic field and a Brownian particle.

Closer analogies had already been noted in the work of R.R. Rubin and R.E. Turner [2, 3, 6], who studied the motion of a particle interacting with a lattice of nearest-neighbour coupled oscillators (with an oscillator chain in the one-dimensional case). These analogies became equivalences when the ratio m/M of the oscillator mass to the particle mass tended to zero in a suitable manner, as shown by S. Takeno and J. Hori [8] and others.

The first model capable of describing a general dissipative environment (with linear dissipation) was, however, proposed only later, within the functional formulation of quantum mechanics, by R.P. Feynman and F.L. Vernon [9]. This model deserves particular attention because it consists of a central degree of freedom in **simultaneous interaction** with an infinite series of harmonic oscillators characterised by an **arbitrary frequency distribution** $G(\omega)$.

Unlike models in which the particle interacts with a lattice of oscillators, the interaction here is “long-range”, in the sense that the central degree of freedom interacts with all oscillators present.

The freedom in the choice of the distribution $G(\omega)$ constitutes a substantial step forward in the description of dissipative environments, both from the classical and the quantum point of view.

For the first time one has a classical mechanical model that, as will be shown in Chapter 1, automatically incorporates the fluctuation–dissipation theorem of non-equilibrium statistical mechanics in its most general form [23, 24, 47], proposed, moreover, only a few years after the Feynman–Vernon model.

In order to incorporate this feature, however, statistical assumptions about the initial conditions of the oscillators must be made. For this reason the model cannot be considered a “purely mechanical model”. What matters for the purposes of quantisation, however, is that these statistical assumptions do not concern the dynamics of the environmental degrees of freedom.

The corresponding quantum model, thanks to the possibility of integrating over the environmental degrees of freedom, has proved to be extremely flexible, as its applications to the most varied physical situations demonstrate. For brevity, these will not be discussed below (in particular, the vast field of quantum tunnelling in the presence of dissipation will not be treated); instead, quantum Brownian motion in the strict sense will be studied, even though the results to be presented are of general applicability.

One fact that makes the Feynman–Vernon model particularly important is that in general the reduced density matrix of a subsystem does **not** satisfy any differential equation. In these cases the quantum description via functional integrals can be extremely advantageous.

Why this oscillator model, with the appropriate hypotheses, represents a general environment with linear dissipation so well is a question that will not be addressed in this work.

Attention will instead be focused on a set of topics which, for clarity, have been divided into two parts: a first, general part (Chapters 1, 2 and 3), in which certain intrinsic features of the model are studied, and a second, applied part (Chapters 4, 5 and 6), in which the results of the first part are applied to situations of various kinds.

Throughout the work the functional approach to quantum mechanics will be followed, which requires only knowledge of the classical Lagrangian of the system. Hence the great importance of the type of classical model used, to which Chapter 1 is entirely devoted.

In the remainder of the first part the issue of the initial correlation between particle and environment is considered.

In the early works on quantum Brownian motion [9, 12, 22] it was assumed that no correlation was present between the initial state of the Brownian particle and the initial state of the dissipative environment. “Absence of correlation” means, in the present context, that the density matrix of the entire system at the initial instant can be expressed as the product of a function of the coordinates of the central particle alone and another function of the coordinates of the thermal bath oscillators alone.

With the work of V. Hakim and V. Ambegaokar [17], in which it was shown that the presence of an initial correlation can have observable effects on the dynamics of a dissipative system, this issue became the subject of numerous investigations.

In several subsequent works [20, 21, 22] formalisms and computational procedures well suited to the study of models with initial correlations and oscillator frequency spectra of very general form were developed.

In the present work it is shown that the hypothesis of absence of initial correlation cannot be formulated in any case. Even under the simplest hypothesis in which the initial density matrix of the total system factorises into the product of the density matrices of the two subsystems – central particle and environment – the correlation is necessarily present.

This result is closely connected to the translational invariance of the problem, as illustrated in Chapter 1 for the classical model and in Chapter 2 for the quantum case.

If this initial correlation is neglected, the consequences can be significant. For example, the classical limit of the motion of a wave packet is not recovered, since its centre of mass does not follow the classical equation and therefore violates Ehrenfest’s theorem, as will be illustrated in Chapter 3.

The results obtained are applied in the second part to a question raised, through some general considerations on quantum mechanics, in a work by G. Jona-Lasinio and P. Claverie [57]. The starting observation is that according to the laws of quantum mechanics any body, microscopic or macroscopic, is destined sooner or later to delocalise indefinitely.

This leads to contradictions with Ehrenfest’s theorem, since it implies that after a sufficiently long time the validity of classical mechanics ceases to hold even on a macroscopic scale.

Contradictions of an experimental nature can also be found regarding the behaviour of microscopic and mesoscopic objects, and further ones are illustrated in detail in Chapter 4. However, it is shown that the key element for understanding the “classical behaviour” of microscopic bodies is dissipation. In particular it is shown that the uncertainty in the position of a mesoscopic or macroscopic body interacting

with the environment asymptotically “crystallises” to a constant value.

In Chapter 5 (carried out in collaboration with F. Illuminati, University of Padua) the case of a particle in an electric field is studied, as well as the more complex but more realistic situation in which a coupling exists not only between the particle and the external field, but also between the environment and the external field. Depending on the type of interaction, the consequences for the dynamics of the central particle can be substantial.

The work concludes with Chapter 6, which reports the results of the study of a two-dimensional problem. The motion of a charged (scalar and non-relativistic) particle in a dissipative environment in the presence of a magnetic field is considered (this work is a collaboration with V. Penna, University of Turin, and E. Barone and P. Sodano, University of Perugia).

Part I:
Theory

Chapter 1: Classical model

This chapter is devoted to the study of the classical model, for which a simple re-derivation is proposed below. More precisely, the “classical Feynman–Vernon model” will be studied, represented by the Lagrangian of the total system {central particle + environment} used in reference [9].

The reasons that led to studying the Feynman–Vernon model in a classical setting are several:

- first of all, it is a model that, accompanied by appropriate statistical initial conditions for the oscillators, describes a **general** linear dissipative environment (at present it is indeed the only known mechanical model possessing this property), and this property has been unjustly overlooked, perhaps because the quantum aspects of the problem have always been the main focus of study;
- the functional formulation of quantum mechanics, which will be employed later, is based on knowledge of the classical Lagrangian. It is therefore essential to formulate the classical model correctly because, as will be seen in Chapter 2, it provides indispensable guidance for setting up the quantum case correctly, avoiding certain procedural errors and bringing notable simplifications to the study of dissipative quantum systems;
- furthermore, the classical treatment is formally identical to the approach to dissipative quantum systems through the “quantum Langevin equation” [10, 11, 12, 18, 20], obtainable formally by replacing the classical variables with the corresponding quantum operators.

Before beginning the specific study of the model, it is useful – in order to outline what the end-point of Chapter 1’s discussion should be – to make a brief digression recalling some particular concepts of non-equilibrium statistical mechanics to which we shall return frequently.

Reference is made to the Langevin method for the description of Brownian motion [42].

The method is based on the classical equation of motion of a particle in a generic external potential $V(x)$, derivable from the Lagrangian of the isolated system. To it are added two terms: the first is a force $-M\gamma\dot{x}$, where M is the mass of the particle and γ the damping coefficient, representing the **dissipation** term responsible for damping the motion; the second is a stochastic force $R(t)$, representing the

fluctuation term and modelling the random interactions with the molecules of the environment:

$$M\ddot{x}(t) + M\gamma\dot{x}(t) + V'(x(t)) = R(t) \quad (1.1)$$

The stochastic force of the Langevin equation is defined by its statistical properties:

1. it is a stationary process, i.e. the correlation $\langle R(t) R(s) \rangle$, where the symbol $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes a statistical average over all configurations of the thermal bath, is a function of the difference $(t - s)$ alone;

2. the mean value is zero:

$$\langle R(t) \rangle = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

3. the statistical correlation $\langle R(t) R(s) \rangle$ between the values of the stochastic force R at two different times is always zero except when $t = s$:

$$\langle R(t) R(s) \rangle = \frac{2M\gamma}{\beta} \delta(t - s) \quad (1.3)$$

where $\beta^{-1} = kT$ is the absolute temperature measured in energy units.

The Langevin equation is, however, only a limit (for sufficiently large M) of a more general equation, usually referred to as the “generalised Langevin equation”, which describes the motion of a particle under the action of stochastic forces whose correlation function $\langle R(t) R(s) \rangle$, as is generally the case for a dissipative system, is a certain (non-singular) function of the difference $t - s$.

The equation referred to is characterised by a time-non-local dissipation term and was introduced by H. Mori [23] and R. Kubo [24]:

$$M\ddot{x}(t) + V'(x(t)) = - \int_{t_0}^t ds \dot{x}(s) u(t - s) + R(t) \quad (1.4)$$

It differs from the Langevin equation in that the dissipative force $-M\gamma\dot{x}$ is replaced by a **memory** term that depends on the history of the particle.

The information concerning the effects of the environment on the particle is contained in the functions $u(t-s)$ and $R(t)$. These two functions are not independent but are related in a direct and simple way by the fluctuation–dissipation theorem. It can be proved by consistency arguments and can be stated in the following way [24, 46] for the classical case:

$$u(t - s) = \beta \langle R(t) R(s) \rangle \quad (1.5)$$

One can easily see that the Langevin equation (1.1) is a particular case of (1.4) in which $u(t-s) = 2M\gamma\delta(t-s)$. Equation (1.5) then reduces to (1.3).

The existence of such a relation is entirely natural; on the contrary, it would be strange if the interaction with the environment, which is by hypothesis the **only** cause of the deviation of the form of the equation of motion from the Lagrange equation, generated **two** distinct and independent terms. Fluctuation and dissipation share the same physical origin, being the stochastic part and the systematic part of the same interaction, and equation (1.5) establishes their relation quantitatively.

It is nonetheless useful to be able to distinguish between effects due to dissipation and fluctuation effects. This distinction does not contradict the fluctuation-dissipation theorem but is in the same spirit as the Langevin equation, since the two effects are physically distinguishable even though they share a common origin.

As an example, an external stochastic force (generated by a circuit subject to thermal fluctuations) produces fluctuation effects but not dissipation. Conversely, a body in a dissipative environment will certainly experience the effect of dissipation, but fluctuations will be negligible if its mass is sufficiently large (macroscopic limit).

One can now proceed to the study of the oscillator model.

Consider the Lagrangian of a system – in one dimension – consisting of a central particle with coordinate x and mass M interacting linearly with N harmonic oscillators q_1, \dots, q_N of mass m (the assumption that all oscillator masses are equal does not cause any loss of generality) characterised by the following Lagrangian:

$$L(x, \dot{x}, \{q_n, \dot{q}_n\}) = \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2 - V(x) + \sum_n \left[\frac{1}{2}m\dot{q}_n^2 - \frac{1}{2}m\omega_n^2 q_n^2 + c_n q_n x \right] \quad (1.6)$$

Models in which quadratic interactions between the oscillators q_1, q_2, \dots are also present (as for example in [10, 11]) are no more general than the one considered here, since by a linear transformation of the q_1, q_2, \dots it is always possible to bring the Lagrangian back to the diagonal form (1.6).

The question to be answered is: in the limit in which the number of oscillators tends to infinity, do there exist initial conditions \dot{q}_{no}, q_{no} such that the equation of motion for $x(t)$ derived from the Lagrangian (1.6) turns out to be equivalent to the Langevin equation?

If so, one would have the remarkable example of an exactly solvable mechanical model of a dissipative system.

Before proceeding to analyse the model represented by the Lagrangian (1.6), it may immediately be noted that the Lagrangian as written is not in general translationally invariant, and for this reason can never correctly represent a thermal bath.

This is also connected to the problem of the “renormalised potential” raised repeatedly in the literature on classical and quantum Brownian motion [12, 14].

Indeed the Lagrangian (1.6) can be rewritten as:

$$L(x, \dot{x}, \{q_n, \dot{q}_n\}) = \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2 - V(x) + \frac{1}{2}k_e x^2 + \sum_n \left\{ \frac{1}{2}m\dot{q}_n^2 - \frac{1}{2}m\omega_n^2 \left(q_n - \frac{c_n x}{m\omega_n^2} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (1.7)$$

While the last term represents an attractive interaction between the particle and the oscillators, as required by the very definition of the model, a new harmonic (repulsive) potential has appeared, characterised by an effective elastic constant $k_e = \sum_n c_n^2/m\omega_n^2$. A Lagrangian of this form evidently makes no physical sense, since it predicts a repulsive force on the central particle starting from the origin of coordinates.

The introduction of a renormalised potential incorporating the new term [14], together with possible assumptions about the potential $V(x)$ that would be required to prevent the renormalised potential from becoming repulsive [12], does not clarify or resolve the problem. Indeed the remaining quadratic term is still non-translationally-invariant: if the reference frame is changed, it generates a new interaction term of the particle with the origin of coordinates.

The only way to avoid such situations is to ensure that the oscillators q_n of the above Lagrangian have their equilibrium point at the central particle x . In any other case (with any other equilibrium point) they will inevitably produce “renormalisation” potentials generating effective forces that depend on the chosen reference frame, as in the case of the repulsive force in (1.7).

Similar considerations taking translational invariance into account are found in several works [10, 11, 17, 18, 20, 21] and all lead to the same lagrangiana:

$$L(x, \dot{x}, \{q_n, \dot{q}_n\}) = \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2 - V(x) + \sum_n \left\{ \frac{1}{2}m\dot{q}_n^2 - \frac{1}{2}m\omega_n^2(q_n - x)^2 \right\} \quad (1.8)$$

This Lagrangian represents a particle to which a “cloud” of oscillators interacting with harmonic forces is attached (see Figures 1 and 2), as emphasised in [20, 21].

It is easy to verify that this is the unique Lagrangian, for a quadratic interaction, that is invariant under translation and spatial reflection (the external potential $V(x)$ is of course not in general translationally invariant). Furthermore it provides a physically suggestive picture of the infinite-oscillator model: the motion of a particle interacting with the environment is equivalent to the free motion of a central particle together with a set of oscillators attached to it, which through their oscillations exert a random influence on the trajectory of the central particle.

Figure 1.1: Visualisation of the mechanical model (physically correct) corresponding to the Lagrangian: $L_o = \frac{M}{2}\dot{x}^2 + \sum_n \left[\frac{m}{2}\dot{q}_n^2 - \frac{m\omega^2}{2}(q_n - x)^2 \right]$

Figure 1.2: Visualisation of the mechanical model (incorrect because not invariant under translations and/or reflections) corresponding to the Lagrangian: $L_o = \frac{M}{2}\dot{x}^2 + \sum_n \left[\frac{m}{2}\dot{q}_n^2 - \frac{m\omega^2}{2}q_n^2 + c_n q_n x \right]$

When the number of oscillators is taken to be infinite, transforming the values of the frequencies $\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots$ into a continuous set $\omega \in (0, \infty)$ and correspondingly introducing a frequency density $G(\omega)$ such that:

$$\sum_n \longrightarrow \int_0^\infty d\omega G(\omega) \quad (1.9)$$

the irreversible character of the particle motion will emerge.

Now consider the Lagrange equations associated with the Lagrangian (1.8):

$$M\ddot{x} + V'(x) = - \sum_n m\omega_n^2(x - q_n) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -k_e x + \sum_n m\omega_n^2 q_n \quad (1.10)$$

$$\ddot{q}_n + \omega_n^2 q_n = \omega_n^2 x \quad (1.11)$$

where the effective elastic constant has been introduced:

$$k_e = \sum_n m\omega_n^2 \quad (1.12)$$

The solution of the system (1.10), (1.11) can be obtained by first solving equation (1.11) for the n -th oscillator q_n , which is the equation of a forced harmonic oscillator in which the external force is proportional to the coordinate x of the central particle, and then substituting its solution into (1.10). The solution for the oscillator q_n is:

$$q_n(t) = q_{no} \cos[\omega_n(t - t_o)] + \frac{\dot{q}_{no}}{\omega_n} \sin[\omega_n(t - t_o)] + \omega_n \int_{t_o}^t ds x(s) \sin[\omega_n(t - s)] \quad (1.13)$$

where $q_{no} = q_n(t_o)$ and $\dot{q}_{no} = \dot{q}_n(t_o)$.

Inserting this solution into the equation of motion for $x(t)$ one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} & M\ddot{x}(t) + V'(x(t)) + k_e x(t) \\ &= \int_{t_o}^t ds x(s) \alpha_1(t - s) + \sum_n m\omega_n^2 \left\{ q_{no} \cos[\omega_n(t - t_o)] + \frac{\dot{q}_{no}}{\omega_n} \sin[\omega_n(t - t_o)] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (1.14)$$

where the function $\alpha_1(t - s)$, which will also play an important role in the quantum model, has been introduced and defined as:

$$\alpha_1(t - s) = \sum_n m\omega_n^3 \sin[\omega_n(t - s)] \quad (1.15)$$

It is now useful to define the correlation function $u(\tau)$:

$$\alpha_1(\tau) = \sum_n m\omega_n^3 \sin(\omega_n\tau) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -\frac{d}{d\tau}u(\tau) \quad (1.16a)$$

$$\text{where: } u(\tau) = \sum_n m\omega_n^2 \cos(\omega_n\tau) \quad (1.16b)$$

Integrating by parts equation (1.14) and noting that $u(0) = k_e$, the “renormalisation force”, which attracted the particle towards the origin of coordinates, disappears, as was to be expected on the basis of the translational invariance of the Lagrangian. One obtains an equation formally identical to the generalised Langevin equation (1.4):

$$\begin{aligned} & M\ddot{x}(t) + V'(x(t)) \\ &= -\int_{t_o}^t ds u(t-s) \dot{x}(s) + \sum_n m\omega_n^2 \left\{ (q_{no} - x_o) \cos[\omega_n(t - t_o)] + \frac{\dot{q}_{no}}{\omega_n} \sin[\omega_n(t - t_o)] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (1.17)$$

provided the stochastic force $R(t)$ is defined as follows:

$$R(t) = \sum_n m\omega_n^2 \left\{ (q_{no} - x_o) \cos[\omega_n(t - t_o)] + \frac{\dot{q}_{no}}{\omega_n} \sin[\omega_n(t - t_o)] \right\} \quad (1.18)$$

By its very definition, $R(t)$ is a translationally invariant function, i.e. it does not depend on the position x but only on the time t . The second term arising from the integration by parts ensures that the q_{no} are replaced by $q_{no} - x_o$. From its properties one could have immediately deduced that $R(t)$ could not depend on the initial coordinates q_{no} of the oscillators but only on the difference $q_{no} - \bar{q}$, where \bar{q} is a certain constant representing a coordinate.

The dependence of $R(t)$ on the differences $q_{no} - x_o$ is essential for obtaining the correct generalised Langevin equation, as is easily seen from (1.17) and (1.18), and as was first specified in the work of P. Mazur and E. Braun [11] and in that of G.W. Ford, M. Kac and P. Mazur [10].

Its implications at the quantum level are equally important, as will be shown in detail in Chapters 2 and 3.

This definition of the stochastic force $R(t)$ has not, however, always been employed, and in particular has had no counterpart in the quantum model [12, 15, 19].

G.W. Ford and M. Kac themselves, in [18], start from the correct Lagrangian and derive (1.17) but consider it valid only for sufficiently large times t , when the second term of the integration by parts has become negligible. Yet their equation is

the correct (generalised) Langevin equation for every value of time t , if the term in question is included in the definition of $R(t)$.

To verify that (1.17) is indeed the generalised Langevin equation, it remains to verify the fluctuation–dissipation theorem.

Explicitly computing the correlation of the stochastic force $R(t)$ from (1.18) one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle R(t) R(s) \rangle &= \\
&= \sum_{in} m\omega_n^2 m\omega_i^2 \left\{ \langle (q_{no} - x_o)(q_{io} - x_o) \rangle \cos[\omega_n(t - t_o)] \cos[\omega_i(s - t_o)] \right. \\
&\quad + \left\langle \frac{\dot{q}_{no}}{\omega_n} \frac{\dot{q}_{io}}{\omega_i} \right\rangle \sin[\omega_n(t - t_o)] \sin[\omega_i(s - t_o)] \\
&\quad + \left\langle (q_{no} - x_o) \frac{\dot{q}_{io}}{\omega_i} \right\rangle \cos[\omega_n(t - t_o)] \sin[\omega_i(s - t_o)] \\
&\quad \left. + \left\langle \frac{\dot{q}_{no}}{\omega_n} (q_{io} - x_o) \right\rangle \sin[\omega_n(t - t_o)] \cos[\omega_i(s - t_o)] \right\} \quad (1.19)
\end{aligned}$$

At this point the statistical ingredient of the model enters. Even though irreversibility arises from the continuous limit of the frequencies ω_n , the type of initial conditions on the oscillators is the element allowing one to obtain a stochastic force $R(t)$ and a correlation function $u(t - s)$ with the desired statistical properties.

If $R(t)$ is a stochastic force, it follows from (1.18) that the variables q_{no} and \dot{q}_{no} are also random variables. The statistical average over the thermal bath ensemble $\langle \dots \rangle$ at the initial instant $t = t_o$ translates into a statistical average over the variables q_{no} and \dot{q}_{no} .

The simplest hypothesis is that at time $t = t_o$ the oscillators are in independent thermal equilibrium according to the Maxwell–Boltzmann distribution for a classical oscillator. Since according to the Lagrangian (1.8) the position of the central particle x is the equilibrium point of the oscillators, the probability distribution is:

$$p(q_{1o}, \dot{q}_{1o}; q_{2o}, \dot{q}_{2o}; \dots) = \prod_n p(q_{no}, \dot{q}_{no}) \quad (1.20a)$$

$$p(q_{no}, \dot{q}_{no}) = \frac{m\omega_n}{2\pi kT} \exp \left\{ -\frac{m\dot{q}_{no}^2}{2kT} - \frac{m\omega_n^2(q_n - x_o)^2}{2kT} \right\} \quad (1.20b)$$

All cross terms $\langle \dots \rangle_{i \neq n}$ with $i \neq n$ therefore factorise into the product of the

averages $\langle \dots \rangle_i \langle \dots \rangle_n$. Taking into account the equipartition theorem [29]:

$$\langle q_n - x_o \rangle = 0 \quad (1.21)$$

$$m\omega_n^2 \langle (q_n - x_o)^2 \rangle = \beta^{-1} \quad (1.22)$$

$$\langle \dot{q}_n \rangle = 0 \quad (1.23)$$

$$m \langle \dot{q}_n^2 \rangle = \beta^{-1} \quad (1.24)$$

it follows that (1.19) reduces to:

$$\langle R(t) R(s) \rangle = \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_n m\omega_n^2 \cos[\omega_n(t - s)] \quad (1.25)$$

Comparing with (1.16b) it can be noted that this expression is exactly equal to $u(t - s)/\beta$ and therefore verifies the fluctuation–dissipation theorem, equation (1.5).

It thus emerges that in the infinite harmonic-oscillator thermal bath model, under the hypothesis that at the initial instant the oscillators are in independent thermodynamic equilibrium and have their equilibrium point on the central particle, **the fluctuation–dissipation theorem is automatically satisfied irrespective of the specific form of the spectral density $G(\omega)$.**

It is interesting to note in this regard that the generalised Langevin equation and the fluctuation–dissipation theorem in its most general form were proposed [23, 24] as a description of classical Brownian motion only a few years later and independently of the harmonic oscillator model, on the basis of non-equilibrium statistical mechanics considerations.

Having examined these general aspects, one may ask which specific forms of the distributions $G(\omega)$ lead to the stochastic differential equations describing Brownian motion.

The answer naturally depends on the type of stochastic equation to which reference is made.

If one considers the Langevin equation, it has already been noted that it is equivalent to a generalised Langevin equation with correlation function $u(t - s) = 2M\gamma \delta(t - s)$. From the definition of the function $u(\tau)$, equation (1.16b), one can easily verify that the white noise density $G_B(\omega)$ is given by:

$$G_B(\omega) = \frac{2M\gamma}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{m\omega^2} \quad (1.26)$$

from which:

$$u(\tau) = \sum_n m\omega_n^2 \cos(\omega_n \tau) \longrightarrow \int_0^\infty d\omega G_B(\omega) m\omega^2 \cos(\omega\tau) = 2M\gamma \delta(\tau) \quad (1.27)$$

A second type of noise that will be studied both for its applicative interest and because it is exactly solvable is that of a Lorentzian density $G_L(\omega)$, corresponding to the Drude model, which differs from (1.26) by a factor proportional to $1/(w^2 + \omega^2)$, where w represents an ultraviolet cut-off frequency (for examples of applications to quantum Brownian motion see [16, 19]):

$$G_L(\omega) = \frac{2M\gamma}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{m\omega^2} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + (\omega/w)^2} \quad (1.28)$$

The corresponding correlation function $u(\tau)$ is given by ($\tau > 0$):

$$u(\tau) = \int_0^{+\infty} d\omega G_L(\omega) m\omega^2 \cos(\omega\tau) = \frac{2M\gamma}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} d\omega \frac{\cos(\omega\tau)}{1 + (\omega/w)^2} = 2M\gamma w e^{-w\tau} \quad (1.29)$$

and decays exponentially as its argument increases, with a decay time $\tau_w = 1/w$.

For $w \rightarrow \infty$ one has $w e^{-w\tau} \simeq \delta(\tau)$ and the white noise limit is recovered.

In Chapter 3 the quantum motion of a free particle in a thermal bath with the above types of noise will be studied. It is useful to briefly summarise the solution of the corresponding classical problem in view of a later comparison.

More precisely it is useful to study the solutions of the “macroscopic equations” of free motion, which describe the time evolution of the mean coordinate $\langle x(t) \rangle$ of the particle.

These are obtained by applying the statistical average $\langle \dots \rangle$ to the Langevin equation (and recalling that $\langle R(t) \rangle = 0$). They formally coincide with those obtained by removing the stochastic force $R(t)$ only for linear Langevin equations, as for example is the case of the free particle. In these cases they represent the limit of negligible fluctuations, $M \rightarrow \infty$.

The macroscopic equations are often presented as the equations describing the “classical” motion of a particle in the presence of friction, ignoring the fluctuation–dissipation theorem; in the following the term “macroscopic” will be preferred, reserving the term “classical” for what concerns the non-quantum treatment of dissipative environments.

The macroscopic equation associated with the Langevin equation (1.1) (noise of

type 1) for a free particle ($V = 0$) is:

$$\ddot{x}(t) + \gamma \dot{x}(t) = 0 \quad (1.30)$$

The corresponding macroscopic trajectory $x(t)$ with initial conditions $x(t_o) = x_o$ and $\dot{x}(t_o) = \dot{x}_o$ is given by:

$$x(t) = x_o + \frac{\dot{x}_o}{\gamma} [1 - e^{-\gamma(t-t_o)}] \quad (1.31)$$

Note that the asymptotic value is $x(\gamma(t - t_o) \gg 1) = x_o + \dot{x}_o/\gamma$.

The macroscopic equation for a free particle in the case of the exponential correlation function (1.29) is instead:

$$\ddot{x}(t) + \gamma w \int_{t_o}^t ds \dot{x}(s) e^{-w(t-s)} = 0 \quad (1.32)$$

Introducing the function:

$$f_1(t) = \gamma w \int_{t_o}^t ds \dot{x}(s) e^{-w(t-s)} \quad (1.33)$$

equation (1.32) can be rewritten simply as $\ddot{x} = -f_1$. Differentiating f_1 with respect to time gives:

$$\dot{f}_1(t) = \gamma w \dot{x}(t) - w f_1(t) \quad (1.34)$$

from which f_1 can be expressed in terms of \dot{f}_1 and \dot{x} ; substituting into $\ddot{x} = -f_1$ gives:

$$\ddot{x}(t) = \frac{\dot{f}_1(t)}{w} - \gamma w \dot{x}(t) \quad (1.35)$$

Integrating between t_o and t and noting that $f_1(t_o) = 0$, f_1 can finally be expressed as a function of x and \dot{x} ; substituting back into $\ddot{x} = -f_1$ one obtains:

$$\ddot{x}(t) + w[\dot{x}(t) - \dot{x}_o] + \gamma w[x(t) - x_o] = 0 \quad (1.36)$$

which is the equation for a damped harmonic oscillator. The solution $x(t)$ is:

$$x(t) = x_o + \frac{\dot{x}_o}{\gamma} \left\{ 1 - e^{-\frac{w}{2}(t-t_o)} \left[\text{ch}[\delta(t-t_o)] + \frac{w/2 - \gamma}{\delta} \text{sh}[\delta(t-t_o)] \right] \right\} \quad (1.37)$$

where:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\left(\frac{w}{2}\right)^2 - \gamma w} \quad (1.38)$$

is assumed to be real. It is useful, for what follows, to rewrite the above macroscopic solutions $x(t)$ as:

$$x(t) = x_o + \frac{\dot{x}_o}{\gamma} \Delta(t - t_o) \quad (1.39)$$

where $\Delta(\tau)$ is a function taking the initial value $\Delta(0) = 0$ and tending asymptotically to one: $\Delta(\infty) = 1$. For Lorentzian noise and white noise ($w \rightarrow \infty$) one has respectively:

$$\Delta(\tau) = 1 - e^{-\frac{w}{2}\tau} \left[\text{ch}(\delta\tau) + \frac{w/2 - \gamma}{\delta} \text{sh}(\delta\tau) \right] \longrightarrow \quad (1.40a)$$

$$\xrightarrow{w \rightarrow \infty} 1 - e^{-\gamma\tau} \quad (1.40b)$$

For both types of noise the asymptotic limit, i.e. for $\gamma(t - t_o) \gg 1$, gives $x(\infty) = x_o + \dot{x}_o/\gamma$, i.e. the distance Δx travelled by the particle is:

$$\Delta x = x(\infty) - x_o = \dot{x}_o/\gamma \quad (1.41)$$

One last point worth elaborating is the following: it was assumed that the mean value of the initial velocities of the oscillators $\langle \dot{q}_{no} \rangle$ is zero, equation (1.23).

One wishes to verify that it is indeed zero and that nothing analogous to what was said about the mean value $\langle q_{no} \rangle$ of the coordinates occurs (one might think of a mean value $\langle \dot{q}_{no} \rangle = \bar{v}$ with $\bar{v} \neq 0$, linked for example to the initial velocity of the central particle).

Indeed, if $R(t)$ in (1.18) is redefined with $\dot{q}_{no} - \bar{v}$ in place of \dot{q}_{no} , a new force term ΔF appears, which in the case of Lorentzian noise is given by:

$$\Delta F = \bar{v} \sum_n m \omega_n \sin[\omega_n(t - t_o)] = \frac{2M\gamma\bar{v}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty d\omega \frac{\sin[\omega(t - t_o)]}{\omega} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + (\omega/w)^2} \quad (1.42)$$

Rewriting $\sin[\omega(t - t_o)]/\omega$ as:

$$\frac{\sin[\omega(t - t_o)]}{\omega} = \int_{t_o}^t ds \cos[\omega(t - t_o)] \quad (1.43)$$

one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta F &= \frac{2M\gamma\bar{v}}{\pi} \int_{t_o}^t ds \int_0^\infty d\omega \frac{\cos[\omega(s - t_o)]}{1 + (\omega/w)^2} = M\gamma w \bar{v} \int_{t_o}^t ds \exp[-w(s - t_o)] \\ &= M\gamma\bar{v}(1 - e^{-w(t-t_o)}) \longrightarrow M\gamma\bar{v} \end{aligned} \quad (1.44)$$

for $w(t - t_o) \gg 1$. Since the limit of ΔF turns out to be independent of w , it holds

for both the Lorentzian and the white noise case. One concludes that if $\langle \dot{q}_{no} \rangle = \bar{v}$, a constant force $\Delta F = M\gamma\bar{v}$ will appear.

It is known [24, 31] (and easily shown by solving the respective macroscopic equation) that a constant force induces an asymptotic drift velocity (for $t \rightarrow \infty$) proportional to the applied force given by:

$$v_{\text{deriva}} = \frac{\Delta F}{M\gamma} = \frac{M\gamma\bar{v}}{M\gamma} = \bar{v} \quad (1.45)$$

which thus turns out to be equal to \bar{v} .

Since a particle subject to the action of friction ends its trajectory with zero velocity relative to the environment, \bar{v} evidently represents the velocity of the environment relative to the reference frame used.

If the reference frame is chosen to coincide with that of the dissipative environment, then one must have

$$\bar{v} = 0 \quad (1.45b)$$

Summarising in one sentence the conclusions on the initial conditions of the thermal bath oscillators, one can say that:

at the initial instant $t = t_o$ the harmonic oscillators of the thermal bath are in independent thermodynamic equilibrium with one another, distributed around the coordinate x of the central particle which represents their equilibrium point, and with zero mean velocity relative to the environment.

For clarity, summary tables are given below concerning the initial statistical conditions of the harmonic oscillators of the thermal bath and the two types of noise, white and Lorentzian, that will be studied.

$$(\beta = 1/kT)$$

INITIAL STATISTICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE OSCILLATORS

$$\begin{aligned}\langle q_n - x_o \rangle = 0 & \quad m\omega_n^2 \langle (q_n - x_o)(q_m - x_o) \rangle = \beta^{-1} \delta_{nm} & \quad \langle \dot{q}_n (q_m - x_o) \rangle = 0 \\ \langle \dot{q}_n \rangle = 0 & \quad m \langle \dot{q}_n \dot{q}_m \rangle = \beta^{-1} \delta_{nm}\end{aligned}$$

WHITE NOISE

$$\begin{aligned}G_B(\omega) &= \frac{2M\gamma}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{m\omega^2} \\ u(\tau) &= \beta \langle R(\tau)R(0) \rangle = 2M\gamma \delta(\tau) \\ M\ddot{x}(\tau) + M\gamma \dot{x}(\tau) + V'(x(\tau)) &= R(\tau)\end{aligned}$$

LORENTZIAN NOISE

$$\begin{aligned}G_L(\omega) &= \frac{2M\gamma}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{m\omega^2} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + (\omega/w)^2} \\ u(\tau) &= \beta \langle R(\tau)R(0) \rangle = 2M\gamma w e^{-w\tau} \\ M\ddot{x}(\tau) + M\gamma w \int_0^\tau d\sigma \dot{x}(\sigma) e^{-w(\tau-\sigma)} + V'(x(\tau)) &= R(\tau)\end{aligned}$$

Chapter 2: Quantum model

In this chapter the quantum version of the classical model presented in the preceding chapter is studied.

It is based on the pioneering work of R.P. Feynman and F.L. Vernon [9, 33], where a general dissipative linear environment is studied, and on that of A.O. Caldeira e A.J. Leggett [14], where the model of Feynman-Vernon is applied to quantum Brownian motion with white noise.

The path-integral formalism is indeed particularly well suited to the elimination of the environmental degrees of freedom.

It requires only knowledge of the classical action of the system, and the results obtained in the preceding chapter within classical Brownian motion allow the quantum case to be set up.

The problem to be faced – that of the interaction between the central particle and the infinite degrees of freedom of the environment – is mathematically no more complicated than the problem in which the particle interacts with a single degree of freedom. In order not to burden the formulae unnecessarily, the discussion will first be developed around the simpler problem in which **the central particle** x interacts with a single **harmonic oscillator** q which, for the moment, will constitute “the environment”. Only at the end will one pass to the sum over all oscillators.

Since the particle is a subsystem of the total system {particle x + environment oscillator q }, a quantum description of its dynamics cannot be based on a wave function $\psi(x, t)$ but only on the reduced density matrix $\varrho(x_1, x_2, t)$.

The reduction is performed by integrating the density matrix of the total system $\varrho(x_1, x_2, q_1, q_2; t)$ on the oscillator coordinate q , after setting $q_1 = q_2 = q$ [45]:

$$\varrho(x_1, x_2, t) = \int dq \varrho(x_1, x_2, q, q, t) \quad (2.1)$$

How does the reduced density matrix $\varrho(x_1, x_2, t)$ evolve in time? The answer to this question is the quantum counterpart of the Langevin equation or of the corresponding Fokker–Planck equation.

As will be shown, the evolution of the reduced density matrix is determined by an effective propagator $\mathcal{K}_e(b|a) = \mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b|x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a)$, in analogy with what

happens for the wave function:

$$\varrho(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b) = \int dx_{1a} dx_{2a} \mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) \varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) \quad (2.2)$$

where $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a)$, the reduced density matrix of the particle at time $t = t_a$, represents the initial state of the particle. It is to be considered arbitrary.

The effective propagator \mathcal{K}_e contains all information on the dynamical evolution of the central particle interacting with the environment.

If the particle were isolated, in the sense of having no interaction with the environment, the density matrix $\varrho(x_1, x_2, t)$ would evolve as the product $\psi(x_1, t) \cdot \psi^*(x_2, t)$ of the two wave functions of the particle [27], and correspondingly the effective propagator would coincide with the product $\mathcal{K}_o(b|a)$ of the two quantum propagators of the wave function:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_o(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) &= K(x_{1b}, t_b | x_{1a}, t_a) K^*(x_{2b}, t_b | x_{2a}, t_a) \\ &= \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar}(S_o[x_1] - S_o[x_2])\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

where $S_o[x]$ represents the action of the central particle in the absence of interaction with other degrees of freedom; a free action $S_o[x]$ of the form

$$S_o[x] = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2} M \dot{x}^2(t) - V(x(t)) \right\} \quad (2.4)$$

is assumed, where $V(x(t))$ is a generic external potential.

In the case where the particle interacts with the environment the propagator $\mathcal{K}_e(b|a)$, although it naturally does not coincide with that $\mathcal{K}_o(b, a)$ of the isolated system, can be expressed in a form closely recalling it:

$$\mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) = \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar}[S_o[x_1] - S_o[x_2]]\right\} \mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2] \quad (2.5)$$

where $\mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2]$ is a functional, in general non-factorisable, of $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$, defined as the ‘‘influence functional’’ [9, 33]. It can be noted that if $\mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2] \equiv 1$ the effective propagator reduces to that (2.3) of the isolated system. All effects of the external environment (represented in this specific case by the harmonic oscillator q) on the particle are therefore encapsulated in the influence functional.

Since knowledge of $\mathcal{K}_e(b|a)$ rests, at least in principle, on knowledge of $\mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2]$, the influence functional is the central quantity of interest in the study of quantum Brownian motion. Together with the action $S_o[x]$ of the isolated system, it is all

that is needed to describe the quantum mechanics of the particle interacting with a dissipative environment.

The remainder of this section is devoted to the computation of the influence functional, which will be carried out in three main steps:

- A) determination of the density matrix of the total system at the initial instant $t = t_a$;
- B) evolution of the density matrix of the total system from $t = t_a$ to $t = t_b$;
- C) elimination of the oscillator coordinate.

A) For the determination of the form of the density matrix $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, q_{1a}, q_{2a}; t_a)$ at the initial instant $t = t_a$, the considerations of the preceding section on the translational invariance of the classical model are indispensable. In the classical model the central particle was characterised by arbitrary initial conditions x_o and \dot{x}_o , while the oscillators were in thermodynamic equilibrium, oscillating around the central particle.

A simple hypothesis will be made that mirrors the conditions in the classical case, namely that at $t = t_a$ the density matrix is given by the product of the density matrix of the central particle (arbitrary) and that of the environment (of the harmonic oscillator q in thermodynamic equilibrium with its equilibrium point on the central particle); it should be stressed immediately that this is not equivalent to a hypothesis of absence of correlation, because the equilibrium point of the harmonic oscillator coincides with the position of the central particle.

In formulae one assumes:

$$\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, q_{1a}, q_{2a}, t_a) = \varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) \cdot \varrho_\beta(q_{1a} - \bar{q}, q_{2a} - \bar{q}) \quad (2.6)$$

where:

1. $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a)$ represents the state of the central particle at $t = t_a$ and corresponds to the initial conditions x_a, \dot{x}_a of the classical case; in general it must be freely choosable. In what follows, the evolution of a density matrix corresponding to the wave function of a Gaussian wave packet of width σ_o with mean values of position and velocity $\langle x(t_a) \rangle = x_o$ and $\langle \dot{x}(t_a) \rangle = \hbar k_o/M$ will be studied; in this case (with normalisation $\int dx \varrho(x, x, t_a) = 1$) one has:

$$\varrho_x(x_{1a}, x_{2a}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_o^2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{(x_{1a} - x_o)^2}{4\sigma_o^2} - \frac{(x_{2a} - x_o)^2}{4\sigma_o^2} + ik_o(x_{1a} - x_{2a}) \right\} \quad (2.7)$$

2. $\varrho_\beta(q_1 - \bar{q}, q_2 - \bar{q})$ is the density matrix of a quantum harmonic oscillator q in thermodynamic equilibrium at absolute temperature $kT = \beta^{-1}$, with its equilibrium point at \bar{q} , which represents the position of the central particle and must be expressed as a function of the coordinates x_{1a} and x_{2a} .

It is known that the density matrix of a harmonic oscillator with its equilibrium point at the origin and in thermodynamic equilibrium (normalised so that $\int dq \varrho_\beta(q, q) = 1$) is given by [33]:

$$\varrho_\beta(q_{1a}, q_{2a}) = \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar \coth(\beta\hbar\omega/2)}} \exp\left\{-\frac{m\omega}{2\hbar} \left([q_{1a}^2 + q_{2a}^2] \coth(\beta\hbar\omega) - \frac{2q_{1a}q_{2a}}{\sinh(\beta\hbar\omega)} \right)\right\} \quad (2.8)$$

The same density matrix for a harmonic oscillator whose equilibrium point has coordinate \bar{q} is obtained by the simple translation $q \rightarrow q - \bar{q}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho_\beta(q_{1a} - \bar{q}, q_{2a} - \bar{q}) &= \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar \coth(\beta\hbar\omega/2)}} \\ &\times \exp\left\{-\frac{m\omega}{2\hbar} \left([(q_{1a} - \bar{q})^2 + (q_{2a} - \bar{q})^2] \coth(\beta\hbar\omega) - \frac{2(q_{1a} - \bar{q})(q_{2a} - \bar{q})}{\sinh(\beta\hbar\omega)} \right)\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

One must now determine how \bar{q} depends on the variables x_{1a} and x_{2a} . For reasons of translational invariance one must have $\bar{q} = c_1 x_{1a} + c_2 x_{2a}$, with c_1 and c_2 constants such that $c_1 + c_2 = 1$. The exchange of the coordinates $1 \leftrightarrow 2$ in a generic density matrix $\varrho(1, 2)$ has the effect that $\varrho(1, 2) = \varrho^*(2, 1)$. Since the oscillator matrix $\varrho_\beta(q_{1a} - \bar{q}, q_{2a} - \bar{q})$ is real, it must be symmetric under the exchange $1 \leftrightarrow 2$. It follows that \bar{q} must also be so, and therefore:

$$\bar{q} = \frac{x_{1a} + x_{2a}}{2} \quad (2.10)$$

It can easily be verified that for $q_{1a} = q_{2a} = q$ and $x_{1a} = x_{2a} = x$ one obtains the correct probability distribution for a quantum oscillator q oscillating around the position x [5]:

$$\varrho_\beta(q - x, q - x) = \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar \coth(\beta\hbar\omega/2)}} \exp\left\{-\frac{m\omega}{2\hbar} (q - x)^2 \coth(\beta\hbar\omega)\right\} \quad (2.11)$$

It is furthermore clear from its definition that $\varrho_\beta(q_1 - \bar{q}, q_2 - \bar{q})$ preserves the normalisation condition of $\varrho_\beta(q_1, q_2)$:

$$\int dq \varrho_\beta(q - \bar{q}, q - \bar{q}) = 1 \quad (2.12)$$

which is essential if one wants $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a)$ to represent effectively the initial reduced matrix for the central particle ($\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) = \int dq_a \varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, q_a, q_a, t_a)$).

What has been said so far about the initial density matrix of the oscillator, summarisable in (2.9) and (2.10), is the quantum counterpart of the initial statistical conditions of the classical case for the coordinates of the harmonic oscillators (summarised on page 27).

It can be noted, by expanding the squares $(q_1 - \bar{q})^2$ and $(q_2 - \bar{q})^2$, with $\bar{q} = \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_2)$, that $\varrho_\beta(q_{1a} - \bar{q}, q_{2a} - \bar{q})$ contains a **non-factorisable initial correlation** between the central particle and the environment. In other words, although the initial density matrix of the total system $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, q_{1a}, q_{2a}, t_a)$ factorises into the product of the two density matrices of (2.6), the initial correlation is nevertheless present.

This point is central to the present chapter and is essential to the formulation of a simple but correct prescription for studying the dynamics of a generic dissipative quantum system, when knowledge of the initial state of the system under study is limited to the reduced density matrix of the central particle, $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a)$.

The introduction of functional formulations of the initial conditions [19, 21, 22] was motivated precisely by recognition of the importance of the initial correlation between particle and environment, which was considered absent when the initial density matrix was assumed to be the product of the density matrix of the environment and that of the central particle.

But this is true only if $\bar{q} = 0$ is assumed in (2.9), which is equivalent to the physically incorrect hypothesis that the oscillators have their equilibrium point at the origin of coordinates.

B) Now consider the time evolution of the density matrix of the total system from the initial instant $t = t_a$ to a generic instant $t = t_b$.

The density matrix $\varrho(x_1, x_2, q_1, q_2, t)$ of the system {particle + oscillator} evolves in time as the product of the two wave functions $\psi(x_1, q_1, t)\psi^*(x_2, q_2, t)$ [27] since the total system is by definition isolated.

This implies that its time evolution follows the law:

$$\begin{aligned} & \varrho(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, q_{1b}, q_{2b}, t_b) \\ &= \int dx_{1a} dx_{2a} dq_{1a} dq_{2a} \mathcal{K}(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, q_{1b}, q_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, q_{1a}, q_{2a}, t_a) \varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, q_{1a}, q_{2a}, t_a) \end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

where $\mathcal{K}(b|a)$ is the propagator of the total density matrix and is given by the

product of the two quantum propagators of the wave function of the total system:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{K}(b|a) &= \mathcal{K}(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, q_{1b}, q_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, q_{1a}, q_{2a}, t_a) \\
&= K(x_{1b}, q_{1b}, t_b | x_{1a}, q_{1a}, t_a) K^*(x_{2b}, q_{2b}, t_b | x_{2a}, q_{2a}, t_a) \\
&= \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{q_{1a}}^{q_{1b}} \mathcal{D}q_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \int_{q_{2a}}^{q_{2b}} \mathcal{D}q_2 \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} (S[x_1, q_1] - S[x_2, q_2]) \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.14}$$

where $S[x, q]$ represents the action of the total system.

From the Lagrangian (1.8) of the preceding chapter one can derive the action for the central particle x interacting with a single oscillator q of frequency ω :

$$S[x, q] = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2} M \dot{x}^2(t) - V(x(t)) + \frac{1}{2} m \dot{q}^2(t) - \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 [x(t) - q(t)]^2 \right\} \tag{2.15}$$

i.e. $S[x, q] = S_o[x] + S_1[q, x]$, where the actions S_o and S_1 have been defined:

$$S_o[x] = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2} M \dot{x}^2(t) - V(x(t)) - \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 x^2(t) \right\} \tag{2.16}$$

$$S_1[q, x] = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2} m \dot{q}^2(t) - \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 q^2(t) + m \omega^2 q(t)x(t) \right\} \tag{2.17}$$

through which the propagator \mathcal{K} of the density matrix of the complete system can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{K}(b|a) &= \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} [S_o[x_1] - S_o[x_2]] \right\} K^*(q_{2b}, t_b | q_{2a}, t_a; [x_2]) K(q_{1b}, t_b | q_{1a}, t_a; [x_1])
\end{aligned} \tag{2.18}$$

where $K(q_b, t_b | q_a, t_a; [x])$ is the quantum propagator for the forced harmonic oscillator q on which acts the external force $m\omega^2 x(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
K(q_b, t_b | q_a, t_a; [x]) &= \int_{q_a}^{q_b} \mathcal{D}q \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} S_1[q, x] \right\} \\
&= \int_{q_a}^{q_b} \mathcal{D}q \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left[\frac{1}{2} m \dot{q}^2(t) - \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 q^2(t) + m \omega^2 q(t)x(t) \right] \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.19}$$

C) It is now possible to find a general expression for the effective propagator $\mathcal{K}_e(b|a)$ and hence for the influence functional $\mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2]$.

Substituting the total propagator (2.18) and the initial density matrix (2.6) into equation (2.13), which gives the evolution at a generic time t_b , and then performing the reduction according to (2.1), one arrives at an expression for the propagator $\mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a)$ formally identical to (2.5) if the influence functional is identified with:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2] &= \int dq_b \int dq_{1a} dq_{2a} K^*(q_b, t_b | q_{2a}, t_a; [x_2]) K(q_b, t_b | q_{1a}, t_a; [x_1]) \varrho_\beta(q_{1a} - \bar{q}, q_{2a} - \bar{q}) \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

(note however that $S_o[x]$ defined in (2.16) does not coincide with the action of the isolated system (2.4) because it also includes the “renormalisation potential” $\frac{1}{2}m\omega^2 x^2$).

Expression (2.20) is general because a formally similar expression would be obtained also for other forms of the particle–oscillator interaction and independently of the specific form of the initial density matrix of the oscillator.

In the present case, the interaction is quadratic and the propagator that appears is that of the forced harmonic oscillator [37]:

$$\begin{aligned} K(q_b, t_b | q_a, t_a; [x]) &= \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{2\pi i\hbar \sin(\omega\tau)}} \exp \left\{ \frac{im\omega}{2\hbar \sin(\omega\tau)} \left((q_b^2 + q_a^2) \cos(\omega\tau) - 2q_a q_b \right. \right. \\ &\quad + 2q_a \omega \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt x(t) \sin[\omega(t_b - t)] + 2q_b \omega \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt x(t) \sin[\omega(t - t_a)] \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \omega^2 \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds x(t)x(s) \sin[\omega(t_b - t)] \sin[\omega(s - t_a)] \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

(where $\tau = t_b - t_a$), and the density matrix $\varrho_\beta(q_1 - \bar{q}, q_2 - \bar{q})$ is that of a harmonic oscillator in thermodynamic equilibrium given in (2.8). The details of the calculations are reported in Appendix A and the result is:

$$\mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2] = \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \Phi[x_1, x_2] \right\} \quad (2.22)$$

where the functional $\Phi[x_1, x_2]$, called the influence phase [9], is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi[x_1, x_2] = & -\frac{m\omega^2}{2}(x_{1a} + x_{2a}) \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt [x_2(t) - x_1(t)] \cos[\omega(t - t_a)] \\ & - \frac{m\omega^3}{2} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x_2(t) - x_1(t)] \sin[\omega(t - s)][x_1(s) + x_2(s)] \\ & + \frac{im\omega^3}{2} \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right) \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x_2(t) - x_1(t)] \cos[\omega(t - s)][x_2(s) - x_1(s)]\end{aligned}\quad (2.23)$$

This expression is not translationally invariant, but when it is substituted into the final expression for the effective propagator (2.5) together with the actions $S_o[x_1]$ and $S_o[x_2]$, one obtains:

$$\mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) = \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar}\mathcal{Y}[x_1, x_2]\right\} \quad (2.24)$$

where $\mathcal{Y}[x_1, x_2]$ is an explicitly translationally invariant functional given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{Y}[x_1, x_2] = & S_o[x_1] - S_o[x_2] + \Phi[x_1, x_2] \\ = & \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}_1^2(t) - \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}_2^2(t) - V(x_1(t)) + V(x_2(t)) \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2[x_1(t) - x_a]^2 + \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2[x_2(t) - x_a]^2 \right\} \\ & - \frac{m\omega^3}{2} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x_2(t) - x_1(t)] \sin[\omega(t - s)][(x_1(s) - x_{1a}) + (x_2(s) - x_{2a})] \\ & + \frac{im\omega^3}{2} \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right) \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x_2(t) - x_1(t)] \cos[\omega(t - s)][x_2(s) - x_1(s)]\end{aligned}\quad (2.25)$$

From (2.25) the expression for the effective propagator for an infinite number of oscillators with natural frequencies $\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n, \dots$ can be readily derived through RULE 2 of the influence functionals [9]:

“The influence functional of a set of statistically and dynamically independent degrees of freedom is the product of the respective influence functionals.”

Equivalently one can say that the influence phase is obtained by summing the respective influence phases of the oscillators (it should be noted for precision that in the present case the respective renormalisation potentials $\frac{1}{2}m\omega_n^2 x_{1,2}^2$ in the actions S_o must also be summed).

Equation (2.24) therefore continues to hold, but the functional \mathcal{Y} is now given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Y}[x_1, x_2] = & \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2} M \dot{x}_1^2(t) - \frac{1}{2} M \dot{x}_2^2(t) - V(x_1(t)) + V(x_2(t)) \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{1}{2} k_e [x_1(t) - x_a]^2 + \frac{1}{2} k_e [x_2(t) - x_a]^2 \right\} \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x_2(t) - x_1(t)] \alpha_1(t-s) [(x_1(s) - x_{1a}) + (x_2(s) - x_{2a})] \\ & + i \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x_2(t) - x_1(t)] \alpha_2(t-s) [x_2(s) - x_1(s)] \end{aligned} \quad (2.26)$$

where the effective elastic constant $k_e = \sum_n m \omega_n^2$ and the function: $\alpha_1(t-s) = \sum_n m \omega_n^3 \sin[\omega_n(t-s)]$ are the same as those introduced in the classical model, equations (1.12) and (1.15), while:

$$\alpha_2(t-s) = \sum_n \frac{1}{2} m \omega_n^3 \coth\left(\frac{\beta \hbar \omega_n}{2}\right) \cos[\omega_n(t-s)] \quad (2.27)$$

The functions $\alpha_1(\tau)$ and $\alpha_2(\tau)$ introduced here correspond to the functions $-\alpha_I(\tau)$ and $\alpha_R(\tau)$ respectively of the work of A.O. Caldeira and A.J. Leggett [14].

Expression (2.26) for the effective propagator is to be compared with that obtained under the hypothesis of absence of correlation (see for example [14]). The latter can be obtained from (2.26) by setting $x_{1a} = x_{2a} = 0$.

Equations (2.24) and (2.26) should be considered the natural quantum counterpart of the classical model presented in Chapter 1. With the appropriate definitions of k_e , $\alpha_1(\tau)$ and $\alpha_2(\tau)$, they represent a result valid for a particle moving under the action of a generic external potential $V(x(t))$ in a dissipative environment characterised by the distribution $G(\omega)$.

The consequences of the dependence of the initial oscillator density matrix on x_{1a} and x_{2a} , absent in the non-correlation hypothesis ($\bar{q} = 0$), on the evolution of the reduced density matrix $\varrho(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b)$, will be clarified in the following chapter.

The explicit forms of the functions $\alpha_1(\tau)$ and $\alpha_2(\tau)$ and of the effective constant k_e in the case of white and Lorentzian noise can be obtained from the densities $G_B(\omega)$, $G_L(\omega)$ (page 31) and are summarised for clarity in the table below.

$$\text{WHITE NOISE} \quad k_e = \frac{2M\gamma}{\pi} \cdot \int d\omega = \frac{2M\gamma \Omega_c}{\pi} \quad (\Omega_c = \Omega_{\text{cut-off}})$$

$$\alpha_1(\tau) = -2M\gamma \delta'(\tau)$$

$$\alpha_2(\tau) = \frac{M\gamma}{\pi} \int d\omega \omega \cos(\omega\tau) \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right)$$

$$\text{“Limit } \beta\hbar w \ll 1\text{”}: \alpha_2(\tau) \simeq \frac{M\gamma}{\beta\hbar} \delta(\tau)$$

$$\text{LORENTZIAN NOISE} \quad k_e = M\gamma w$$

$$\alpha_1(\tau) = 2M\gamma w^2 e^{-w\tau}$$

$$\alpha_2(\tau) = \frac{M\gamma}{\pi} \int d\omega \frac{\omega \cos(\omega\tau)}{1 + (\omega/w)^2} \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right)$$

$$\text{“Limit } \beta\hbar w \ll 1\text{”}: \alpha_2(\tau) \simeq \frac{M\gamma w}{\beta\hbar} \exp(-w\tau)$$

* * *

The “Limit $\beta\hbar w \ll 1$ ” requires an explanation in the case of white noise.

Indeed in this case the correlation time $\tau_w = 1/w$ is by definition zero (i.e. $w = \infty$), so that the classicality condition $\beta\hbar w \ll 1$ cannot hold.

In practice, however, speaking of “white noise” has the physical meaning that $\tau_w \ll \tau$, where τ is the relaxation time of the system, so that there does exist a critical temperature $1/\beta^*$ above which the above approximation holds.

This limit should therefore be considered, for reasons of consistency, as a particular limit of Lorentzian noise obtained first as the classical limit ($\beta\hbar w \ll 1$), then as the white noise limit ($\tau \gg 1/w$), i.e. $\tau \gg 1/w \gg \hbar\beta = \hbar/kT$.

* * *

Chapter 3: Free particle

The present chapter is the natural complement to Chapters 1 and 2. The particular case of the free particle is considered, for which (2.24) and (2.26) hold with $V(x(t)) = 0$, in order to study in a specific example the consequences of the considerations made on translational invariance and initial correlation.

Since the action $\mathcal{Y}[x_1, x_2]$ appearing in equation (2.24) is quadratic in the variables $x_1(t)$, $x_2(t)$, it can be easily shown [13], by expanding $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$ in series around the classical trajectories $\bar{x}_1(t)$ and $\bar{x}_2(t)$, that the effective propagator is determined by the corresponding classical action $\mathcal{Y}_c = \mathcal{Y}[\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2]$:

$$\mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) = F(\tau) \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{Y}_c\right\} \quad (3.1)$$

where the factor $F(\tau)$ depends only on $\tau = t_b - t_a$ and, for the moment, is not known.

The classical action is computed in detail in Appendix B in the case of Lorentzian noise (and hence, by taking the limit $w \rightarrow \infty$, in the case of white noise).

It is worth making a brief digression on the advantages of using Lorentzian noise over white noise.

The exponential correlation function is first of all of great general interest as it represents a realistic model of many physical systems (the Drude model) to the point that it can be considered typical, and it is the most general form of exponential correlation for a Markovian process [41]. The white noise limit, on the other hand, is valid only under the hypothesis that the system under study is characterised by a correlation time much shorter than the relaxation time.

Furthermore there are mathematical reasons that make it necessary to avoid both the white noise limit, in which no cut-off frequency exists for the oscillator distribution, and the ‘‘Debye-type’’ model [56], in which the oscillator density is assumed equal to that of white noise up to $\omega \leq \Omega_c$, where Ω_c is a cut-off frequency, and identically zero for $\omega > \Omega_c$.

The reason for these mathematical complications can be seen clearly in equation (2.26): as $t_a \rightarrow t_b$, it is natural that the contribution of the double integrals should tend to zero.

Using instead the above-mentioned densities, $\alpha_1(t-s)$ becomes equivalent to the derivative of a Dirac delta, and automatically the double integral gives a non-zero

contribution, even for $t_a = t_b$, of the same order of magnitude as the other terms.

The Lorentzian density $G(\omega) \propto 1/[1 + (\omega/w)^2]$, page 31, avoids such problems. Moreover, after the elimination of the double integrals (see Appendix B) it is not necessary to continue the calculation with the Lorentzian distribution and one can safely return to the white noise approximation without incurring any of the ambiguities mentioned.

Finally it is worth noting that, by generating an exponential correlation function $\alpha_1(\tau) \propto e^{-w\tau}$, the classical problem, and hence also the quantum one, becomes exactly solvable in the case of quadratic Lagrangians (see Appendix B).

It is convenient to express the effective propagator \mathcal{K}_e not through the variables x_1 and x_2 but through the auxiliary variables:

$$x = \frac{x_1 + x_2}{2}, \quad \xi = x_2 - x_1 \quad (3.2)$$

Correspondingly the effective propagator will be written as $\mathcal{K}_e(x_b, \xi_b, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a)$ and the density matrix as a function $\varrho(x, \xi, t)$ of the variables x, ξ .

If one is interested in the probability density $p(x_b, t_b)$ it is sufficient to compute the effective propagator of the density matrix $\mathcal{K}_e(x_b, \xi_b, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a)$ for $\xi_b = 0$, since this is equivalent to setting $x_{1b} = x_{2b} = x_b$:

$$p(x_b, t_b) = \varrho(x_b, \xi_b = 0, t_b) = \int dx_a d\xi_a \mathcal{K}_e(x_b, \xi_b = 0, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) \varrho(x_a, \xi_a, t_a) \quad (3.3)$$

The result of the calculation, carried out in detail in Appendix B, is:

$$\mathcal{K}_e(x_b, 0, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) = F(\tau) \exp \left\{ \frac{iM\gamma}{\hbar} \left[\frac{(x_b - x_a)\xi_a}{\Delta(\tau)} + i\varepsilon_a(\tau)\xi_a^2 \right] \right\} \quad (3.4)$$

In this expression ε_a is a real constant depending on the various parameters of the model and on $\tau = t_b - t_a$. Since it appears in the exponent in a real term, it contributes exclusively to the fluctuation (in particular to the law governing the spreading of a wave packet). For the moment its form will not be made explicit.

$\Delta(\tau)$ is the same function, characterised by the properties $\Delta(0) = 0$ and $\Delta(\infty) = 1$, that had been introduced with the solution of the macroscopic equation of a free particle in the presence of Lorentzian noise, equation (1.40a).

It contributes both to the fluctuation and to the dissipation (in particular to the time dependence of the mean coordinate $\langle x(t) \rangle$ of a wave packet).

With the effective propagator, through (3.3), it is possible to derive the probability density $p(x_b, t_b)$ corresponding to the initial density matrix associated with a wave packet with $\langle x(t_a) \rangle = x_o$ and $\langle \dot{x}(t_a) \rangle = \hbar k_o/M$ already written in (2.7) and

which in terms of the variables x, ξ is rewritten as:

$$\varrho(x_a, \xi_a, t_a) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_o^2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(x_a - x_o)^2}{2\sigma_o^2} - \frac{\xi_a^2}{8\sigma_o^2} - ik_o\xi_a\right\} \quad (3.5)$$

The integrals to be performed are Gaussian and the result is:

$$p(x_b, t_b) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2(t)}} \exp\left\{-\frac{\left(x_b - x_o - \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{\hbar k_o}{M} \Delta(t)\right)^2}{2\sigma(t)^2}\right\} \quad (3.6)$$

i.e. again a Gaussian packet whose mean position and width vary with time.

In the mean position one recognises precisely the expression of the macroscopic solution (1.39), if in place of the initial velocity \dot{x}_o one puts the mean value $\langle \dot{x}(t_a) \rangle = \hbar k_o/M$.

The width of the Gaussian packet is instead given by:

$$\sigma(\tau)^2 = \sigma_o^2 \left[1 + \frac{M \varepsilon_a(\tau)/\hbar + 1/\sigma_o^2}{(M\sigma_o\gamma/\hbar \Delta(\tau))^2} \right] \quad (3.7)$$

Since $\Delta(\tau)$ tends to one for large τ , the asymptotic behaviour of the width is determined by the function $\varepsilon_a(\tau)$. One sees that in the absence of fluctuation ($\varepsilon_a = 0$) $\sigma(t)^2$ would reach an asymptotic value, but since $\varepsilon_a(\tau)$ is in any case (even for $\beta \rightarrow \infty$) a positive and increasing function of τ , the packet is destined to spread out in any case.

The asymptotic behaviour of $\sigma(\tau)^2$ depends substantially on the infrared behaviour of the oscillator density $G(\omega)$. It has been widely studied in [20, 21] for generic $G(\omega \rightarrow 0) \propto \omega^\alpha$, for general values of α .

The form of $\sigma^2(t)$ will be taken up and studied in more detail for a particular case in Chapter 4.

It is now possible to draw conclusions about the problem of the initial correlation between particle and environment. As already explained in the preceding chapters, “absence of initial correlation” has been understood as the assumption, incorrect for reasons of translational invariance, that the initial density matrix is given by a product of the type $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) \cdot \prod \varrho_\beta(q_{1a}, q_{2a})$ where:

- $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a)$ is the initial density matrix of the central particle;
- $\prod \varrho_\beta(q_{1a}, q_{2a})$ represents the product of the density matrices of the individual oscillators, where the generic $\varrho_\beta(q_{1a}, q_{2a})$ is the density matrix of a harmonic

oscillator in thermodynamic equilibrium **oscillating around the origin of coordinates**. It is equivalent to the density matrix used so far, equation (2.9), with $\bar{q} = 0$.

What are the consequences of such an assumption on the behaviour of the probability density (3.6)? In other words, how are the results obtained for a free particle modified if for the initial density matrix of the oscillators one uses that given in (2.8) ($\bar{q} = 0$) instead of that given in (2.9) ($\bar{q} = \frac{1}{2}(x_{1a} + x_{2a})$)?

As shown in reference [17], the behaviour of the variance $\sigma^2(t)$ differs substantially between the two cases because of the presence of certain terms that persist on a time scale of γ^{-1} , hence directly observable. Otherwise it is “reasonable”, in the sense that $\sigma^2(t)$ is an increasing function of time, i.e. $\sigma^2(\tau) \geq \sigma_o^2$, and at $\tau = 0$ one has $\sigma^2(0) = \sigma_o^2$.

What has not been clarified is that for the mean position of the packet one would obtain the non-physical result $x(\gamma\tau \gg 1) = (\hbar k_o/M\gamma)$ instead of $x(\gamma\tau \gg 1) = x_o + (\hbar k_o/M\gamma)$. The result that would have been obtained suffers from the lack of translational invariance, which naturally reflects the non-translational-invariance of the initial density matrix. As for the mean position of the wave packet at a generic instant τ , one would obtain the solution of the following (non-translationally-invariant) equation:

$$\ddot{x}(\tau) + \gamma w \int_{t_a}^{\tau} ds \dot{x}(s) e^{-w(t-s)} + \gamma w x_a e^{-w(t-t_a)} = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

The reason is that this is precisely the macroscopic equation that would be obtained from the classical oscillator model if one assumed that the equilibrium point of the oscillators is at the origin of coordinates instead of on the central particle. This is easily shown by retracing the steps of Chapter 1 with this assumption.

The conclusion is therefore that the absence of initial correlation not only implies results different from the case in which the correlation is non-zero, but leads to results that are in contradiction with Ehrenfest’s theorem.

It should furthermore be clear, given the nature of the error in question, that this is not only true for a Brownian particle moving in a gas or liquid, as has been assumed up to this point, but in general for any degree of freedom subject to generalised stochastic forces and for which in the classical limit equations similar to the Langevin or generalised Langevin equation hold. One thinks, for example, of the electric charge on a capacitor in an electric circuit, the phase of a Josephson junction, etc.

The reason why this point has not been clarified is in fact rather trivial: the

initial condition $\langle x(t_a) \rangle = x_o = 0$ has always been assumed. It is evident that by setting $x_o = 0$ it is not possible, from the study of the asymptotic limit alone of the mean position of the wave packet, to distinguish between the case with and the case without initial correlation.

It is also not possible to distinguish the two cases by considering the mean position $x_m(\tau)$ at a generic instant of time τ , because, as is easily verified, if the initial mean position is $x_o = 0$ then the $x_m(\tau)$ corresponding to the cases with and without initial correlation coincide, even for Lorentzian noise.

The only quantity that differs is the variance $\sigma^2(\tau)$, whose behaviour, however, as already mentioned, is entirely reasonable and gives no hint of errors unless one knows the correct behaviour in advance in order to compare it with the result obtained.

In light of these observations, the results of the work of V. Hakim and V. Ambegaokar turn out to be of considerable importance, greater than that attributed to them by the authors themselves, who limited themselves to highlighting the differences in the behaviour of $\sigma^2(\tau)$ between the two cases, while they in fact carried out the first calculation on dissipative quantum systems that correctly accounts for the translational invariance of the problem.

Part II:
Applications

Chapter 4: Quantum delocalisation of a body interacting with the environment

The present chapter apparently departs from the thread of the quantum Brownian motion problem to turn to some general questions of quantum mechanics.

According to the laws of quantum mechanics, every isolated body, of arbitrary mass and dimensions, is subject, on a sufficiently long time scale, to delocalising indefinitely. In other words, the probability of detecting it at position x at time t after having detected it at position x_o at time t_o does not depend on x in the limit $t - t_o \rightarrow \infty$.

The time required for an isolated body of mass M simply to double its initial quantum uncertainty σ_o on its position is of the order of $\tau_\sigma = M\sigma_o^2/\hbar$ (see below). If one considers a macroscopic body (say $M = 1$ g) with an initial uncertainty of the order of atomic dimensions ($\sigma_o = 10^{-8}$ cm), one obtains $\tau_\sigma \simeq 10^{11}$ s $\simeq 3000$ years.

For macroscopic bodies, therefore, the quantum delocalisation process does not appear to have directly observable consequences. Nevertheless, the problem of principle remains [57] that complete delocalisation invalidates the classical limit as expressed by Ehrenfest's theorem [55] for the motion of the centre of mass of a wave packet. Indeed, for sufficiently long times it would no longer be possible to speak of the "motion of the wave packet" even for a wave packet associated with a macroscopic body, and the validity of classical mechanics would thereby be undermined.

The situation becomes, however, patently contradictory in the case of microscopic bodies (of atomic dimensions) and mesoscopic bodies (of dimensions intermediate between microscopic and macroscopic). Experience shows that in common laboratory situations they do not delocalise but behave in a substantially classical manner. Consider, for example, the localisation properties of pyramidal molecules such as AsH_3 , discussed in more detail in [57]; the fact that molecules and even single H^+ ions (i.e. simple protons) do not diffuse in a fluid via quantum delocalisation but according to classical diffusion [49]; or, finally, the importance for all of chemistry and biology of the fact that molecules and macromolecules behave, as regards the motion of their centre of mass, in a classical manner.

As already suggested in a work on the effects of a static perturbation on the localisation of a quantum system moving in a double potential well [57], the explanation of this contradiction is to be sought in the interaction of the body with its environment. In this chapter we focus on the dynamical perturbations of the

environment, represented for example by collisions with the molecules of the fluid in which the Brownian particle moves.

The aim is to investigate how external perturbations can modify the type of diffusion to which a quantum system is subject. It will be shown that the interaction with the environment alone is sufficient to account for the classical behaviour even of a single proton diffusing in a fluid.

The results used for this purpose are not new. Although the explicit formulae to be presented are not available in the literature, the delocalisation process of a quantum Brownian particle has been widely studied for very general linear dissipation models [20, 21].

To the best of our knowledge, however, the connection between the problem set out above and the quantum delocalisation properties predicted by quantum Brownian motion theory has never been investigated.

We begin by studying the delocalisation of a body in the simplest case, that in which no external forces act; from there we proceed to seek the possible factors that, for the reasons given above, should inhibit delocalisation.

It will first be shown that the quantum delocalisation of isolated systems occurs in the same way whether the systems are elementary or many-body.

Consider a system of N particles with masses m_1, \dots, m_N , Cartesian coordinates $\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N$, spins $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_N$, interacting with one another through a potential $V(\mathbf{r}_{ij}; \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i)$ depending only on the differences $\mathbf{r}_{ij} = \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j$ and on the spin coordinates.

The system is described by a wave function Ψ , depending on the variables \mathbf{r}_i and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i$, which satisfies a many-body Schrödinger equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = - \sum_i^N \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_i} \Delta_i \Psi + V \Psi \quad (4.1)$$

where the Δ_i are the Laplacians corresponding to the variables \mathbf{r}_i . It is easy to show that it is always possible to separate the problem into that of the motion of the centre of mass, whose coordinates are given by:

$$\mathbf{r}_B = \frac{\sum_i m_i \mathbf{r}_i}{\sum_i m_i} \quad (4.2)$$

and into that of the internal motion, described by the spin coordinates and by another $N - 1$ coordinates $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N-1}$, defined appropriately depending on the problem. As a simple example, the \mathbf{x}_i can be defined as relative coordinates by setting $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1$, $\mathbf{x}_2 = \mathbf{r}_3 - \mathbf{r}_2$, \dots , $\mathbf{x}_{N-1} = \mathbf{r}_N - \mathbf{r}_{N-1}$.

Correspondingly, the wave function is expressed as the product $\Psi(\mathbf{r}_B, \mathbf{x}_i, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i) = \Psi_B(\mathbf{r}_B) \cdot \Psi_R(\mathbf{x}_i, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i)$, where $\Psi_B(\mathbf{r}_B)$ depends solely on the centre-of-mass coordinates \mathbf{r}_B and $\Psi_R(\mathbf{x}_i, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i)$ depends solely on the relative coordinates \mathbf{x}_i and the spins $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i$. If the system is isolated, i.e. no external forces act, $\Psi_B(\mathbf{r}_B)$ satisfies the Schrödinger equation for a free particle:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi_B}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2M} \Delta_B \Psi \quad (4.3)$$

where Δ_B is the Laplacian for the coordinates \mathbf{r}_B and $M = \sum_i m_i$ is the total mass of the system.

Since $\Psi_B(\mathbf{r}_B)$ describes the translational motion through space of the global system, it follows that it also determines its delocalisation properties, which are thus independent of the internal state and identical to those of an isolated elementary particle with mass equal to the total mass M . In what follows, the dynamics of the delocalisation of “a particle of mass M ” is therefore considered.

Consider an initial wave function that is a Gaussian wave packet $\psi(x_a, t_a)$ (in one dimension to keep the formulae simple), characterised by a variance σ_o^2 , a mean coordinate $\langle x(t_o) \rangle = x_o$, and a mean velocity $\langle \dot{x}(t_o) \rangle = \hbar k_o / M$ (normalised so that $\int dx_a |\psi(x_a, t_a)|^2 = 1$):

$$\psi(x_a, t_a) = \frac{1}{[2\pi\sigma_o^2]^{1/4}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(x_a - x_o)^2}{4\sigma_o^2} + ik_o \cdot (x_a - x_o)\right\} \quad (4.4)$$

At time t_b the wave function is again a Gaussian packet, as can easily be verified using the quantum propagator $K_o(x_b, t_b | x_a, t_a)$ for the free particle [34]:

$$K_o(x_b, t_b | x_a, t_a) = \sqrt{\frac{M}{2\pi i \hbar \tau}} \exp\left\{\frac{iM(x_b - x_a)^2}{2\hbar \tau}\right\} \quad (4.5)$$

where $\tau = t_b - t_a$. The associated probability density is:

$$|\psi(x_b, t_b)|^2 = \left| \int dx_a K_o(x_b, t_b | x_a, t_a) \psi(x_a, t_a) \right|^2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma(\tau)^2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{[x_b - \bar{x}(\tau)]^2}{2\sigma(\tau)^2}\right\} \quad (4.6)$$

where $\bar{x}(\tau) = x_o + (\hbar k_o / M)\tau$ is the solution of the corresponding classical problem $\ddot{\bar{x}}(\tau) = 0$ with initial conditions $x(0) = x_o$ and $\dot{x}(0) = \dot{x}_o = \hbar k_o / M$, and $\sigma(\tau)$ is the width of the wave packet at time t_b :

$$\sigma(\tau) = \sqrt{\sigma_o^2 + \left(\frac{\hbar \tau}{2M\sigma_o}\right)^2} = \sigma_o \cdot \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\hbar \tau}{2M\sigma_o^2}\right)^2} \quad (4.7)$$

Quantum mechanics therefore predicts that the wave function associated with the free motion of any physical system disperses indefinitely.

As noted at the start of the chapter, the growth of σ with time is not realistically observable for a macroscopic body. If the ratio $\hbar/M\sigma_o^2$ is however sufficiently large, then for large times σ grows linearly with time, $\sigma(\tau) \simeq \hbar\tau/M\sigma_o$.

Consider the example of a microscopic system, for which quantum diffusion is enhanced: a proton diffusing in H₂O (or a molecule of any gas — the orders of magnitude do not change).

If the proton were treated as an isolated particle with an initial delocalisation $\sigma_o \simeq 10^{-8}$ cm, it would diffuse according to the law $\sigma(\tau) \simeq v_o\tau$ with $v_o = \hbar/M\sigma_o = 63500$ cm/s. This is in clear contradiction with experience, according to which diffusion follows the classical diffusion equation [48], i.e. a law $\sigma(\tau) \simeq \sqrt{2D\tau}$, where $D \simeq 9.31 \cdot 10^{-5}$ cm²/s [34] is the diffusion coefficient at $T \simeq 300$ K.

It is therefore reasonable to conclude that the interaction with the environment plays an essential role in the dynamics of the wave packet.

Just as happens for the proton in question, one can infer that the interaction with the environment is a “localising factor” for mesoscopic and macroscopic bodies, regardless of whether their mass is or is not large enough to make direct observation of their delocalisation possible.

The first thing one might consider, taking the interaction with the environment into account, is how the situation would change if a generic external force $f(t)$ were present. In this case the wave function no longer evolves through the free propagator $K_o(x_b, t_b|x_a, t_a)$ but through the propagator $K(x_b, t_b|x_a, t_a; [f])$ [36]:

$$\begin{aligned} K(x_b, t_b|x_a, t_a; [f]) &= \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \mathcal{D}x \exp\left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left[\frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2(t) + x(t)f(t) \right] \right\} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{M}{2\pi i\hbar\tau}} \exp\left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \left(\frac{M(x_b - x_a)^2}{2\tau} + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt f(t) \frac{x_a(t_b - t) + x_b(t - t_a)}{\tau} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{1}{M\tau} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds f(t)f(s)(t_b - t)(s - t_a) \right) \right\} \quad (4.8) \end{aligned}$$

In this case the calculation leads to the following probability density:

$$|\psi(x_b, t_b)|^2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma(\tau)^2}} \exp\left\{ -\frac{(x_b - \bar{x}(\tau; [f]))^2}{2\sigma(\tau)^2} \right\} \quad (4.9)$$

where $\bar{x}(\tau; [f]) = x_o + (\hbar k_o/M)\tau + (1/M) \int_0^\tau d\tau' (\tau - \tau')f(\tau')$ is the solution of the classical problem $M\ddot{x}(\tau) = f(\tau)$, but the $\sigma(\tau)$ that appears is exactly the same as in the free case ($f(\tau) \equiv 0$), equation (4.7). In other words, for no form of the external

force $f(t)$ is the evolution of the width of the wave packet modified with respect to the free case.

There is more, however: one can imagine external potentials in which the width of a wave packet grows particularly rapidly.

In this regard, recall the result for a Gaussian packet moving in the harmonic potential $V(x) = \frac{1}{2}M\omega^2x^2$ [54, 58]: the probability density is a Gaussian with a mean position given by the classical solution $\bar{x}(t) = x_o \cos(\omega\tau) + (\hbar k_o/M\omega) \sin(\omega\tau)$ and a variance that oscillates in time: $\sigma^2(\tau) = \sigma_o^2(\cos^2(\omega\tau) + (\hbar/2M\omega\sigma_o^2)^2 \sin^2(\omega\tau))$.

From these formulae one can immediately derive those for a repulsive potential $V(x) = -M\omega^2x^2/2$ simply by setting $\omega \rightarrow i\omega$. The classical solution $\bar{x}(\tau)$ becomes that corresponding to the repulsive potential, while for the variance one obtains:

$$\sigma^2(\tau) = \sigma_o^2 \left\{ \text{ch}^2(\omega\tau) + \left(\frac{\hbar}{2M\omega\sigma_o^2} \right)^2 \text{sh}^2(\omega\tau) \right\} \xrightarrow{\omega\tau \gg 1} \frac{\sigma_o^2}{4} \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{\hbar}{2M\omega\sigma_o^2} \right)^2 \right\} e^{2\omega\tau} \quad (4.10)$$

i.e. it grows exponentially with time for $\omega\tau \gg 1$. The delocalisation process could in this case be spectacular.

It is also notable that the asymptotic behaviour is essentially independent of the mass of the body, since even in the limit $M \rightarrow \infty$ one would have $\sigma^2(\tau) \simeq \frac{1}{4}\sigma_o^2 \cdot e^{2\omega\tau}$.

A repulsive potential such as the one just considered is not as peculiar as it might seem. For example, the centrifugal potential experienced by a body in a non-inertial reference frame rotating at constant angular velocity ω (and constrained to a radial trajectory) is precisely of that form.

Any repulsive potential in general causes the width of the wave packet to increase, the faster the more rapidly the potential decreases with distance.

It seems unlikely, however, that a macroscopic body would delocalise simply because it had been for some time under the action of a potential of this type. It is more reasonable to expect that its interaction with the environment keeps it localised, as happens to the proton diffusing in H₂O.

One might object that an important element has been overlooked in the above: the generic force $f(\tau)$ considered is in fact a stochastic quantity, not a deterministic function as assumed. What changes for $\sigma^2(\tau)$ if one assumes $f(\tau)$ to be a stochastic process, which for simplicity will be taken as Gaussian?

Assume $f(\tau) = f_o(\tau) + \phi(\tau)$, where $f_o(\tau)$ is a given function of time and $\phi(\tau)$ is a random contribution with zero mean, $\langle \phi(t) \rangle = 0$, and correlation $\langle \phi(t)\phi(s) \rangle = \mathcal{C} \delta(t - s)$ with \mathcal{C} a positive constant determining the intensity of the fluctuations.

Then $f(\tau)$ is a stochastic process characterised by:

$$\langle f(t) \rangle = f_o(t) \quad (4.11a)$$

$$\langle [f(t) - f_o(t)][f(s) - f_o(s)] \rangle = \mathcal{C} \delta(t - s) \quad (4.11b)$$

The stochastic process $f(\tau)$ can alternatively be defined through the probability functional $P[\bar{f}(t)]$, which gives the probability that the force $f(t)$ takes the particular values corresponding to the function $\bar{f}(t)$. It can be shown that the functional $P[f]$, normalised so that $\langle 1 \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}f P[f] = 1$, is given by [Appendix C]:

$$P[f] = \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\mathcal{C}} \int dt [f(t) - f_o(t)]^2 \right\} \quad (4.12)$$

With the probability functional $P[f]$ one can statistically average the evolution of the wave packet over the possible forms of $f(t)$. The averaging operation, however, must be applied not to the wave function but to the density matrix, which can be directly interpreted in terms of probabilities. It is easy to see that this is equivalent to evolving the density matrix $\varrho(x_1, x_2, t)$ not with its quantum propagator $\mathcal{K}(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a; [f])$ corresponding to a deterministic force $f(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a; [f]) &= K(x_{1b}, t_b | x_{1a}, t_a; [f]) K^*(x_{2b}, t_b | x_{2a}, t_a; [f]) \\ &= \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left[\frac{M}{2} \dot{x}_1^2 - \frac{M}{2} \dot{x}_2^2 + f \cdot (x_1 - x_2) \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

but with its statistical average $\bar{\mathcal{K}} = \int \mathcal{D}f P[f] \mathcal{K}[\dots; f]$. The calculation is simplified by the use of the variables $x = (x_1 + x_2)/2$ and $\xi = x_2 - x_1$. Following the standard method for quadratic actions, one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathcal{K}}(x_b, \xi_b = 0, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) &= \int \mathcal{D}f P[f] \mathcal{K}(x_b, \xi_b = 0, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a; [f]) \\ &= \int \mathcal{D}x \mathcal{D}\xi \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left[-M\dot{x}\dot{\xi} - f_o \cdot \xi + \frac{i\mathcal{C}}{2\hbar} \xi^2 \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (4.17a)$$

$$= F(\tau) \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{M(x_b - x_a)\xi_a}{\tau} - \xi_a \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \frac{t_b - t}{\tau} f_o(t) + \frac{i\xi_a^2 \tau \mathcal{C}}{6\hbar} \right] \right\} \quad (4.17b)$$

where $F(\tau)$ is a normalisation factor.

Note that if the constant \mathcal{C} is set equal to that of the stochastic force associated with white-noise Brownian motion, $\mathcal{C} = 2M\gamma/\beta$, then the term containing \mathcal{C} in (4.17a) becomes equal to that obtained in Appendix A, upon replacing $\alpha_2(t - s)$

by its white noise limit $(2M\gamma/\beta)\delta(t-s)$. Comparing the two, one notices however that the dissipative term — the integral containing $\alpha_1(t-s)$ — is absent.

In other words, even though dissipation is always accompanied by the corresponding fluctuation, the converse is not generally true: an external stochastic force generates only fluctuation but not dissipation.

The problem of the effect of a stochastic force can therefore be stated as follows: is fluctuation alone (without dissipation) sufficient to modify the behaviour of $\sigma^2(\tau)$ with time and in particular to reduce delocalisation?

The answer can be obtained by propagating the usual Gaussian packet given by (4.4), to which corresponds an initial density matrix $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a)$ given by the product $\psi(x_{1a}, t_a) \cdot \psi^*(x_{2a}, t_a)$:

$$\begin{aligned}\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_o^2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(x_{1a}-x_o)^2}{4\sigma_o^2} - \frac{(x_{2a}-x_o)^2}{4\sigma_o^2} + ik_o(x_{1a}-x_{2a})\right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_o^2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(x_a-x_o)^2}{2\sigma_o^2} - \frac{\xi_a^2}{8\sigma_o^2} - ik_o\xi_a\right\}\end{aligned}\quad (4.18)$$

The result is a probability density:

$$\begin{aligned}p(x_b, t_b) &= \varrho_b(x_b, 0, t_b) \\ &= \int dx_a d\xi_a \bar{\mathcal{K}}(x_b, 0, t_b|x_a, \xi_a, t_a) \varrho(x_a, \xi_a, t_a) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma(\tau)^2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(x_b-x_m(\tau))^2}{2\sigma(\tau)^2}\right\}\end{aligned}\quad (4.19)$$

where $x_m(\tau) = x_o + (\hbar k_o/M)\tau + (1/M) \int_0^\tau d\tau' (\tau - \tau') f_o(\tau')$ is the solution of the macroscopic problem $\ddot{x}(\tau) = f_o(\tau)$ for the particle in the presence of the deterministic part $f_o(\tau)$ of the stochastic force $f(\tau)$, while for $\sigma^2(\tau)$:

$$\sigma^2(\tau) = \sigma_o^2 + \left(\frac{\hbar\tau}{2M\sigma_o}\right)^2 + \frac{\mathcal{C}\tau^3}{3M^2}\quad (4.20)$$

The variance thus consists of a first contribution, which is exactly the same as in the absence of fluctuation ($\mathcal{C} = 0$), and a second contribution due to the statistical fluctuations of the external force $f(t)$, which grows with time even faster than the first (being $\propto \tau^3$).

Fluctuation alone therefore only increases the uncertainty in the position of the system. **In conclusion, no external force, whether stochastic or deterministic, can inhibit the delocalisation process in any way.**

But an external force cannot represent the interaction with a dissipative envi-

ronment, since at most it introduces the effect of fluctuations, whereas a dissipative environment is also characterised by dissipation, in accordance with the fluctuation–dissipation theorem. Only by taking both elements into account through an adequate model can one study the real effect of the environment on the delocalisation process.

One naturally returns to the results of the oscillator model which, as described in Chapters 1, 2 and 3, is a realistic model of a general linear dissipative environment and accounts for the fluctuation–dissipation theorem.

Returning to formula (3.7), which expresses the variance of a free wave packet travelling in a dissipative environment, this can be written as:

$$\sigma(\tau)^2 = \sigma_o^2 + \left(\frac{\hbar\Delta(\tau)}{M\sigma_o\gamma} \right)^2 + \frac{\hbar\varepsilon_a(\tau)\Delta^2(\tau)}{M\gamma^2} \quad (4.21)$$

This consists of three contributions, the first of which represents the initial width.

The second term, since $\Delta(\tau \rightarrow \infty) = 1$, reaches the asymptotic value $(\hbar/4M\sigma_o\gamma)^2$, which depends on the damping coefficient γ and the initial width.

The last term is the effect of fluctuation.

As an example, only the limit will now be considered in which $\coth(\beta\hbar\omega/2)$ can be replaced by the reciprocal of its argument, and times $\tau \gg \tau_w = 1/w$ are considered so that the white noise approximation $w \exp(-w\tau) \simeq \delta(\tau)$ can be used. In other words, the “limit $\beta\hbar w \ll 1$ for white noise” will be taken, as described in the table on page 45.

In this limit, ε_a is approximately given by:

$$\varepsilon_a \simeq \frac{2\gamma\tau + 4e^{-\gamma\tau} - 3 - e^{-2\gamma\tau}}{2\hbar\beta[1 - e^{-\gamma\tau}]^2} \xrightarrow{\gamma\tau \gg 1} \frac{\gamma\tau}{\hbar\beta} \quad (4.23)$$

Introducing the classical diffusion coefficient through Einstein’s relation $D = 1/\beta M\gamma$ [50], the limit for $\gamma\tau \gg 1$ of $\sigma^2(\tau)$ is:

$$\sigma^2(\gamma\tau \gg 1) \simeq \sigma_o^2 + \left(\frac{\hbar\beta D}{\sigma_o} \right)^2 + 2D\tau \quad (4.24)$$

Even for an initial delocalisation of order $\sigma_o \simeq 10^{-8}$ cm, the second term, in the case of proton diffusion in H₂O at $\beta^{-1} = 300$ K, amounts to about $(10^{-10} \text{ cm})^2$ and is negligible compared to the third, since $D \simeq 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$.

One can observe that in the case of negligible dissipation ($\gamma \rightarrow 0$), one has $\Delta(\tau)/\gamma \rightarrow \tau$, since $x_m(t) = x_o + \dot{x}_o\Delta(\tau)/\gamma \rightarrow x_o + (\hbar k_o/M)\tau$. It follows that the second term of (4.21) reduces to the second term of (4.20) computed in the absence

of dissipation, which is proportional to τ^2 . Likewise it is easy to verify that the last fluctuation term reduces to the term of (4.20) proportional to τ^3 , if one sets $\mathcal{C} = 2M\gamma/\beta$.

The lesson to be drawn from these considerations is that dissipation, distinct from fluctuation as specified in Chapter 1, is the fundamental element that inhibits delocalisation. One might have thought instead that dissipation, by damping the motion of the particle until its velocity $v \simeq 0$, acts as a delocalising factor because of the uncertainty principle $\Delta x \cdot \Delta(mv) \geq \hbar$. The uncertainty principle in its classical form is, however, valid only for an isolated particle, and the interaction with the environment can substantially modify it.

It is thanks to dissipation that the three terms of (4.20) are transformed into the three terms of (4.24):

1. the initial variance σ_o^2 , which is the same in both equations;
2. the quantum contribution, which in the free case would be $\propto \tau^2$ but which dissipation “crystallises” to the asymptotic limit $(\hbar\beta D/\sigma_o)^2 = (\hbar/M\gamma\sigma_o)^2$; for negligible fluctuations, e.g. for a macroscopic body, this represents the only increment in variance $\Delta\sigma^2 = \sigma^2(\infty) - \sigma_o^2$;
3. the fluctuation contribution. For a “pure fluctuation” this term would be $\propto \tau^3$, but in the presence of dissipation it is “damped” to the classical diffusion law, $\Delta x^2 = 2D\tau$.

What was said in the case of a proton applies even more strongly when larger masses are involved, and thus provides an independent explanation of the absence of delocalisation for a macroscopic body interacting with the environment.

As shown in [20, 21], when the approximation “ $\beta\hbar w \ll 1$ for white noise” used here does not hold, delocalisation occurs even more slowly for the two types of noise treated here (white and Lorentzian).

Chapter 5: Particle in an electric field

In this chapter various situations in which an external (electric) field E is present are considered.

In the simplest case the particle is subject to an external force $f_o(t) = QE_o(t)$, where Q is the electric charge of the particle and $f_o(t)$ is a given function of time. The corresponding results, for the evolution of a wave packet, will be only summarised without detailing the calculations:

- the behaviour of the variance $\sigma^2(t)$ is not modified by the application of an external force;
- in the case of a constant force F_o the wave packet reaches, for $\gamma\tau \gg 1$, a limiting mean velocity given by $\bar{v} = F_o/M\gamma$, in agreement with classical results, both for white noise and for Lorentzian noise.

A more detailed study will instead be made of the situation in which **the oscillators themselves are coupled to an external field**. One wishes to investigate, with a simple model, the consequences of the more realistic hypothesis that applying an external field, besides modifying the dynamics of the central particle, also influences the environment and therefore, indirectly — through the interaction between central particle and environment — has further effects on the particle's motion.

A simplified model will be examined, represented by a Lagrangian containing two terms, representing the Taylor expansion of the interaction Lagrangian in the difference $(q - x)$: one linear, neglected in Chapter 1 for symmetry reasons under spatial reflection, and one quadratic analogous to the particle–oscillator interaction terms already present:

$$L(x, \dot{x}, \{q_n, \dot{q}_n\}) = \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2 - V(x) + \sum_n \left\{ \frac{1}{2}m\dot{q}_n^2 + (q_n - x)f_n(E) - \frac{1}{2}m[\omega_n^2 + \bar{\omega}_n^2(E)](q_n - x)^2 \right\} \quad (5.1)$$

The quantities $f_n(E)$ and $\bar{\omega}_n(E)$, functions of the external field E , determine the intensity with which the external field interacts with the individual modes $\{q_n\}$.

For simplicity it is assumed that the parameters f_n and $\bar{\omega}_n$ do not depend on time. It is useful at this point to introduce the effective frequencies $\Omega_n(E)$, dependent on

the external field, defined as:

$$\Omega_n^2(E) = \omega_n^2 + \bar{\omega}_n^2(E) \quad (5.2)$$

through which the Lagrangian is rewritten as:

$$L(x, \dot{x}, \{q_n, \dot{q}_n\}) = \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2 - V(x) + \sum_n \left\{ \frac{1}{2}m\dot{q}_n^2 + f_n(q_n - x) - \frac{1}{2}m\Omega_n^2(q_n - x)^2 \right\} \quad (5.3a)$$

Separating the Lagrangian in a first part L_o that is independent of q and in the remaining part L_1 , we obtain:

$$L(x, \dot{x}, \{q_n, \dot{q}_n\}) = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}^2 - V(x) - \frac{1}{2}k_e x^2 - f_e x}_{L_o(\dot{x}, x)} + \sum_n \underbrace{\left\{ \frac{1}{2}m\dot{q}_n^2 + q_n[f_n + m\Omega_n^2 x] - \frac{1}{2}m\Omega_n^2 q_n^2 \right\}}_{L_1(\dot{q}_n, q_n, x)} \quad (5.3b)$$

where $f_e = \sum_n f_n$. One sees that the calculation of the influence functional can be carried out following exactly the same procedure as in Chapter 2, provided the driving force of the n -th oscillator, $m\omega_n^2 x(t)$, is replaced by $m\Omega_n^2[x(t) + f_n(t)/m\Omega_n^2]$ and the frequencies ω_n by the rescaled frequencies Ω_n .

Summing the contributions from all oscillators and rearranging, one finally obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{K}_e(x_b, \xi_b, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) \\ &= \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \mathcal{D}x \int_{\xi_a}^{\xi_b} \mathcal{D}\xi \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left(-M\dot{x}\dot{\xi} + V(x + \xi/2) - V(x - \xi/2) \right. \right. \\ &+ k_e[x(t) - x_a]\xi(t) \\ &- \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)[x(s) - x_a]\alpha_1(t-s) + i \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)\xi(s)\alpha_2(t-s) \\ &\left. \left. + \xi(t) \sum_n f_n \cos[\Omega_n(t - t_a)] \right) \right\} \quad (5.4) \end{aligned}$$

Comparing this expression with that of (A.12), one can see that the effects of the interaction of the environment with the external field appear:

1. in the last term, absent in (A.12). It represents, at the classical level, a force opposing the motion of the particle (for positive f_n) which in the case of

Lorentzian noise, is given by:

$$f_E(t) = - \sum_n f_n(E) \cos[\Omega_n(E)(t-t_a)] = \frac{4M\gamma}{\pi} \int d\omega \frac{\cos[\Omega(E, \omega)(t-t_a)]}{1 + (\omega/w)^2} \cdot \frac{f(E, \omega)}{m\omega^2} \quad (5.5)$$

One sees that in order to avoid divergences it is necessary to assume that the interaction intensities f_n vanish at least as ω_n^2 . Without loss of generality one can set:

$$f(E, \omega) = f_o(E, \omega) \frac{m\omega^2}{2M\omega_o^2} \quad (5.6)$$

where ω_o is a constant and f_o is a function of ω . Equation (5.5) then becomes:

$$f(E, t) = \frac{2\gamma}{\pi\omega_o^2} \int d\omega \frac{\cos[\omega(t-t_a)]}{1 + (\omega/w)^2} f_o(E, \omega) \quad (5.7)$$

which for $f_o = \text{cost}$ becomes $f(t) = (\gamma w/\omega_o^2) f_o e^{-w(t-t_a)}$ and, in the white noise limit, becomes $f(t) = (\gamma/\omega_o^2) \delta(t-t_a)$. In other words it is a transient that decays rapidly. The consequences are nevertheless observable since, among other things, the particle slows down due to the momentum Δp that is subtracted from it, which is non-zero even in the white noise limit: $\Delta p \simeq \int dt f(t) \simeq \gamma/\omega_o^2$.

2. In the functions $\alpha_1(\tau)$, $\alpha_2(\tau)$ and in the elastic effective constant k_e through the rescaling of the frequencies, even if formally the definitions as a function of the Ω_n are equal to those as a function of the ω_n :

$$\alpha_1(t-s) = \sum_n m\Omega_n^3 \sin[\Omega_n(t-s)] \quad (5.8a)$$

$$\alpha_2(\tau) = \sum_n \frac{m\Omega_n^3}{2} \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\Omega_n}{2}\right) \cos(\Omega_n\tau) \quad (5.8b)$$

$$k_e = \sum_n m\Omega_n^2 \quad (5.8c)$$

Varying the external field intensity in this case profoundly affects the structure of the effective propagator.

The modifications to the functions $\alpha_1(\tau)$ and $\alpha_2(\tau)$ are essential and also affect the macroscopic limit of the equations of motion. Indeed, a rescaling of the frequencies is equivalent to a rescaling of the oscillator density $G(\omega)$, which defines the type of noise characterising the dissipative environment in which the particle moves.

Abstracting from the first-order perturbation in $(q_n - x)$, one can express the entire effect of the external field by saying that the function $G(\omega)$ is modified.

Indeed this function enters only through the integration over the frequencies ω ;

if $F(\Omega)$ is a generic function of the rescaled frequency $\Omega(E, \omega) = \sqrt{\omega^2 + \bar{\omega}^2(E, \omega)}$, one has:

$$\int_0^\infty d\omega G(\omega) F(\Omega) \longrightarrow \int_{\bar{\omega}(E)}^\infty d\Omega G\left(\sqrt{\Omega^2 - \bar{\omega}^2(E, \omega)}\right) F(\Omega) \frac{d}{d\Omega} \sqrt{\Omega^2 - \bar{\omega}^2(E, \omega)} \quad (5.9a)$$

which is equivalent to the following transformation for $G(\omega)$:

$$G(\omega) \longrightarrow \bar{G}(\omega') = \Theta(\omega' - \bar{\omega}(E)) G\left(\sqrt{\omega'^2 - \bar{\omega}^2(E, \omega)}\right) \frac{d}{d\omega'} \sqrt{\omega'^2 - \bar{\omega}^2(E, \omega)} \quad (5.9b)$$

where ω is understood as a function of E and Ω defined by the continuum limit of (5.2).

If a situation in which the model could be applied were practically realisable, the interaction between environment and external field could be revealed by varying the external field intensity.

At the conclusion of the chapter another situation will be considered, in which the electric field is itself subject to random fluctuations.

The case in which the particle does not interact with the environment but only with the stochastic electric field has already been widely treated in the literature for a particle in a cavity containing a black-body spectrum (see for example [9]).

If the electric field is instead generated by a circuit containing a voltage generator, it can be shown that the problem is essentially equivalent to that of a particle under the action of a stochastic force, already considered in Chapter 4 for the particular case of white noise.

Consider a particle moving through a region of linear dimension ℓ between the two plates of a capacitor, across which there is a potential difference $ddp = Q_c(t)/C_e$, where $Q_c(t)$ is the charge accumulated on the plates of the capacitor, generating an electric field $E = Q_c(t)/C_e\ell$ and thus a force:

$$f(t) = \frac{Q Q_c(t)}{C_e \ell} \quad (5.10)$$

Suppose that the voltage generator in the circuit to which the capacitor of capacitance C_e is connected can be modelled by an effective resistance R_e , an effective inductance L_e , and an ideal voltage source $\mathcal{V}_o(t)$ (see Figure 3).

The circuit equation describing the time behaviour of the charge $Q_c(t)$ is:

$$L_e \ddot{Q}_c(t) + R_e \dot{Q}_c(t) + C Q_c(t) = \mathcal{V}_o(t) + R_V(t) \quad (5.11)$$

where on the right-hand side the total circuit potential \mathcal{V}_T has been separated into

Figure 5.1: Example of an equivalent circuit generating a stochastic potential.

its systematic part $\mathcal{V}_o(t)$ and the stochastic potential $R_V(t)$ originating from the circuit's thermal fluctuations. Comparing this equation with that of a Brownian harmonic oscillator, $M\ddot{x} + M\gamma\dot{x} + M\omega^2x = f_o(t) + R(t)$, where $f_o(t)$ is a given external force and $R(t)$ is the stochastic force, from relations (1.2) and (1.3) one finds that $R_V(t)$ is a Gaussian stochastic process characterised by:

$$\langle R_V(t) \rangle = 0 \quad (5.12a)$$

$$\langle R_V(t) R_V(s) \rangle = \frac{2R_e}{\beta} \delta(t - s) \quad (5.12b)$$

Denoting by $\mathcal{V}_T(t) = \mathcal{V}_o(t) + R_V(t)$ the total potential applied to the circuit, the first relation shows that $\langle \mathcal{V}_T(t) \rangle = \mathcal{V}_o(t)$.

With this information one can derive the correlation of $Q_c(t)$ and hence study the effect of the stochastic force $f(t)$, defined in (5.1), on the motion of the particle.

Integrating equation (5.2), it is easy to show that in the limit $\gamma(t - t_o) \gg 1$, i.e. at thermal equilibrium:

$$\langle Q_c(t) Q_c(s) \rangle = \frac{C_e}{4\delta\beta} [\Gamma_1 e^{-\Gamma_1(t-s)} - \Gamma_2 e^{-\Gamma_2(t-s)}] \quad (5.13)$$

from which:

$$\langle f(t) f(s) \rangle = \left(\frac{Q}{\ell} \right)^2 \frac{1}{4C_e\delta\beta} [\Gamma_1 e^{-\Gamma_1(t-s)} - \Gamma_2 e^{-\Gamma_2(t-s)}] \quad (5.13b)$$

where $\Gamma_1 = R_e/2L_e + \delta$, $\Gamma_2 = 1/2L_e - \delta$, $\delta = \sqrt{(R_e/2L_e)^2 - 1/L_e C_e}$. The problem is thus reduced to that of a particle under the action of a stochastic force with an exponential correlation function (see [7] for the treatment of a general correlation function), i.e. with Lorentzian-type noise.

Another situation of some interest is when the particle moves under the action

of a stochastic electric field while also being immersed in a dissipative environment.

To this end it is sufficient to average the effective propagator of the reduced density matrix for a particle in a dissipative environment over the possible forms of the external force $f(t)$.

The functional weighting this probability is computed in detail in Appendix C for a Gaussian process. Now consider the form of the effective propagator given by (2.24) and (2.26) in the particular case where a potential $V = -x(t)f(t)$ corresponding to a force $f(t)$ is present and the fluctuation term is approximable by a white noise term:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) \\
&= \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left(\frac{M}{2} [\dot{x}_1^2(t) - \dot{x}_2^2(t)] \right. \right. \\
&\quad - \frac{k_e}{2} [x_1(t) - x_a]^2 + \frac{k_e}{2} [x_2(t) - x_a]^2 \\
&\quad + [x_1(t) - x_2(t)]f(t) + \frac{iM\gamma}{\hbar\beta} [x_2(t) - x_1(t)]^2 \Big) \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x_2(t) - x_1(t)]\alpha_1(t-s)[(x_1(s) - x_{1a}) + (x_2(s) - x_{2a})] \right\} \\
& \tag{5.14}
\end{aligned}$$

Using the functional $P[f]$ one can now average this expression. Proceeding as in Chapter 4 one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \overline{\mathcal{K}_e}(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) \\
&= \int \mathcal{D}f P[f] \mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) \\
&= \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left(\frac{M}{2} [\dot{x}_1^2(t) - \dot{x}_2^2(t)] \right. \right. \\
&\quad - \frac{k_e}{2} [x_1(t) - x_a]^2 + \frac{k_e}{2} [x_2(t) - x_a]^2 \\
&\quad + \frac{i}{\hbar\beta} \left[M\gamma + \left(\frac{Q}{\ell} \right)^2 R_e \right] \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt [x_2(t) - x_1(t)]^2 \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x_2(t) - x_1(t)]\alpha_1(t-s)[(x_1(s) - x_{1a}) + (x_2(s) - x_{2a})] \right) \Big\} \\
& \tag{5.15}
\end{aligned}$$

This result reflects the well-known fact that when two Gaussian noises are superimposed, their respective variances add.

It can be interpreted in terms of an effective mass M^* or in terms of an effective

damping coefficient γ^* given by:

$$\gamma^* = \gamma + \left(\frac{Q}{\ell}\right)^2 \frac{R_e}{M} \quad (5.16)$$

This formula could be experimentally verified by varying the parameters on which γ^* depends.

Chapter 6: Particle in a magnetic field

In this chapter the problem of a particle moving in a dissipative environment in the presence of a constant magnetic field $\mathbf{B} = (0, 0, B)$ directed along the z axis is treated.

It will be assumed that the magnetic field is related, through the relation $\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}$, to a vector potential \mathbf{A} in symmetric gauge:

$$\mathbf{A}(x, y, z) = \left(-\frac{1}{2}By, +\frac{1}{2}Bx, 0\right) \quad (6.1)$$

Since in the absence of external electric potentials the Lagrangian of the system consists of the kinetic terms plus the product $\mathbf{A} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}$, where $\dot{\mathbf{r}}$ is the particle velocity, the motion along the z axis is free motion in a dissipative environment. This case was already treated in Chapter 3; here the analysis is restricted to the problem in the x - y plane.

The quantum propagator of the isolated system (i.e. in the absence of interactions with the environment), available in the literature [36], is:

$$\begin{aligned} K(x_b, y_b, t_b | x_a, y_a, t_a) &= \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \mathcal{D}x \int_{y_a}^{y_b} \mathcal{D}y \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left[\frac{M}{2}(\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2) + \frac{M\omega_B}{2}[xy - yx] \right] \right\} \\ &= F(\tau) \exp \left\{ \frac{iM\omega_B}{4\hbar} \left[[(x_b - x_a)^2 + (y_b - y_a)^2] \cot \left(\frac{\omega_B \tau}{2} \right) + 2[x_a y_b - x_b y_a] \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6.2a)$$

where:

$$F(\tau) = \frac{M\omega_B}{4\pi i \hbar \sin \left(\frac{\omega_B \tau}{2} \right)} \quad (6.2b)$$

The mathematical problem, although two-dimensional, presents no particular difficulties compared to the one-dimensional free particle treated in Chapter 3. Since the treatment proceeds in a very similar way, a detailed exposition analogous to that of Appendices A and B will not be given; only the main steps of the calculation will be recalled.

Since the interaction between the particle with coordinates $(x(t), y(t))$ and the generic environment oscillator with coordinates $(u(t), v(t))$ is proportional to the square of their distance, i.e. $(x - u)^2 + (y - v)^2$, the Lagrangian separates into two independent contributions for the two coordinates, each identical to the one-

dimensional case.

First consider the problem of the particle coupled to a single harmonic oscillator of the thermal bath. The corresponding action is:

$$\begin{aligned}
S[x, y, u, v] &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2} M \dot{x}^2(t) + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{y}^2(t) + \frac{1}{2} m \dot{u}^2(t) + \frac{1}{2} m \dot{v}^2(t) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} M \omega_B [x\dot{y} - y\dot{x}] - \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 [x(t) - u(t)]^2 - \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 [y(t) - v(t)]^2 \right\} \\
&= S_o[x, y] + S_1[u, x] + S_1[v, y]
\end{aligned} \tag{6.3}$$

where the S_1 are the actions of the harmonic oscillators $u(t)$ and $v(t)$ subject to the external forces $m\omega^2 x(t)$ and $m\omega^2 y(t)$ respectively, defined exactly as in (2.17). The action S_o is instead:

$$S_o[x, y] = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2} M [\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2] - \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 [x^2 + y^2] + \frac{1}{2} M \omega_B [x\dot{y} - y\dot{x}] \right\} \tag{6.4}$$

Reasoning analogously to what was done in Chapter 2 for the one-dimensional case, it is easy to show that the reduced density matrix of the central particle $\varrho(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, y_{1b}, y_{2b}, t_b)$ evolves with an effective propagator $\mathcal{K}_e(b|a)$ according to:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\varrho(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, y_{1b}, y_{2b}, t_b) \\
&= \int dx_{1a} dx_{2a} dy_{1a} dy_{2a} \mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, y_{1b}, y_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, y_{1a}, y_{2a}, t_a) \varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, y_{1a}, y_{2a}, t_a)
\end{aligned} \tag{6.5}$$

where $\varrho(x_{1a}, x_{2a}, y_{1a}, y_{2a}, t_a)$ is the initial reduced density matrix. The effective propagator can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, y_{1b}, y_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, y_{1a}, y_{2a}, t_a) \\
&= \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \int_{y_{1a}}^{y_{1b}} \mathcal{D}y_1 \int_{y_{2a}}^{y_{2b}} \mathcal{D}y_2 \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} [S_o[x_1, y_1] - S_o[x_2, y_2]] \right\} \mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2] \mathcal{F}[y_1, y_2]
\end{aligned} \tag{6.6}$$

Its form is analogous to that of the one-dimensional case, with the difference that in passing to two dimensions, instead of a single influence functional two appear, $\mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2]$ and $\mathcal{F}[y_1, y_2]$, defined identically (see equations (2.22) and (2.23)).

When one passes to an infinite number of oscillators, the influence functionals become simply the product of the functionals corresponding to the various oscillators (and the quantity $m\omega^2$ in S_o becomes the effective elastic constant k_e , equa-

tion (1.12)), and the effective propagator becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, y_{1b}, y_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, y_{1a}, y_{2a}, t_a) \\ = \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \int_{y_{1a}}^{y_{1b}} \mathcal{D}y_1 \int_{y_{2a}}^{y_{2b}} \mathcal{D}y_2 \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{Y}[x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2]\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6.7)$$

Setting $\mathbf{r}_1 = (x_1, y_1)$ and $\mathbf{r}_2 = (x_2, y_2)$, the functional \mathcal{Y} can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Y}[x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2] = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left\{ \frac{1}{2} M (|\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1(t)|^2 - |\dot{\mathbf{r}}_2(t)|^2) - \frac{1}{2} k_e (|\mathbf{r}_1(t) - \mathbf{r}_{1a}|^2 - |\mathbf{r}_2(t) - \mathbf{r}_{2a}|^2) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{2} M \omega_B [(x_1 \dot{y}_1 - y_1 \dot{x}_1) - (x_2 \dot{y}_2 - y_2 \dot{x}_2)] \right\} \\ - \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds \alpha_1(t-s) [\mathbf{r}_2(t) - \mathbf{r}_1(t)] \cdot [(\mathbf{r}_1(s) - \mathbf{r}_{1a}) + (\mathbf{r}_2(s) - \mathbf{r}_{2a})] \\ + i \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds \alpha_2(t-s) [\mathbf{r}_2(t) - \mathbf{r}_1(t)] \cdot [\mathbf{r}_2(s) - \mathbf{r}_1(s)] \end{aligned} \quad (6.8)$$

The functions $\alpha_1(\tau)$ and $\alpha_2(\tau)$ are the same as in the one-dimensional case (see page 45).

Since \mathcal{Y} is quadratic, the propagator can be computed exactly as $\mathcal{K}_e(b, a) \propto \exp(i\mathcal{Y}_cl/\hbar)$, where $\mathcal{Y}_cl = \mathcal{Y}[\bar{x}_1, \bar{y}_1, \bar{x}_2, \bar{y}_2]$ is the classical functional, evaluated along the classical trajectories $\bar{x}_1, \bar{y}_1, \bar{x}_2, \bar{y}_2$ defined by the variation $\delta\mathcal{Y} = 0$.

Introducendo le variabili ausiliarie:

$$x = \frac{x_1 + x_2}{2}, \quad \xi = x_2 - x_1, \quad y = \frac{y_1 + y_2}{2}, \quad \eta = y_2 - y_1 \quad (6.9)$$

and assuming a Lorentzian spectrum (pages 31, 45), one arrives at the following classical equations:

$$\ddot{\xi}(t) + \gamma w \xi(t) - \omega_B \dot{\eta}(t) - \gamma w^2 \int_t^{t_b} ds \xi(s) e^{-w(s-t)} = 0 \quad (6.10a)$$

$$\ddot{\eta}(t) + \gamma w \eta(t) + \omega_B \dot{\xi}(t) - \gamma w^2 \int_t^{t_b} ds \eta(s) e^{-w(s-t)} = 0 \quad (6.10b)$$

$$\ddot{x}(t) + \gamma w [x(t) - x_a] - \omega_B \dot{y}(t) - \gamma w^2 \int_{t_a}^t ds [x(s) - x_a] e^{-w(s-t)} + i f_x = 0 \quad (6.10c)$$

$$\ddot{y}(t) + \gamma w [y(t) - y_a] + \omega_B \dot{x}(t) - \gamma w^2 \int_{t_a}^t ds [y(s) - y_a] e^{-w(s-t)} + i f_y = 0 \quad (6.10d)$$

where $f_x(t) = (1/M) \int_0^t dt' \xi(t') \alpha_2(|t-t'|)$ and $f_y(t) = (1/M) \int_0^t dt' \eta(t') \alpha_2(|t-t'|)$ are linear functionals of ξ and η .

To decouple the equations it is useful to introduce the following complex vari-

ables:

$$z = x + iy, \quad \bar{z} = x - iy, \quad \zeta = \xi + i\eta \quad (6.11a)$$

It should be noted that the variables z and \bar{z} are not complex conjugates of each other ($\bar{z} \neq z^*$), since x and y are already complex variables in their own right (as seen from their equations of motion), and that for the same reason both are needed to replace x and y . Since ξ and η are real variables, it suffices to introduce only the variable ζ .

The inverse relations of Eqs.(6.11a) are:

$$\xi = \text{Re}\{\zeta\} = \frac{\zeta + \zeta^*}{2}; \quad \eta = \text{Im}\{\zeta\} = \frac{\zeta - \zeta^*}{2i}; \quad x = \frac{z + \bar{z}}{2}; \quad y = \frac{z - \bar{z}}{2i} \quad (6.12b)$$

The equations satisfied by the new variables are:

$$\ddot{\zeta}(t) + \gamma w \zeta(t) + i\omega_B \dot{\zeta}(t) - \gamma w^2 \int_t^{t_b} ds \zeta(s) e^{-w(s-t)} = 0 \quad (6.13a)$$

$$\ddot{z}(t) + \gamma w [z(t) - z_a] + i\omega_B \dot{z}(t) - \gamma w^2 \int_{t_a}^t ds [z(s) - z_a] e^{-w(s-t)} + i f_o(t) = 0 \quad (6.13b)$$

$$\ddot{\bar{z}}(t) + \gamma w [\bar{z}(t) - \bar{z}_a] - i\omega_B \dot{\bar{z}}(t) - \gamma w^2 \int_{t_a}^t ds [\bar{z}(s) - \bar{z}_a] e^{-w(s-t)} + i f_o^*(t) = 0 \quad (6.13c)$$

where $f_o(t) = (1/M) \int_0^t dt' \zeta(t') \alpha_2(|t - t'|)$.

The fact that z and \bar{z} are not complex conjugates of each other implies that the equations they satisfy are not either. They can, however, be obtained from each other by setting $\omega_B \rightarrow -\omega_B$ and $f_o \rightarrow f_o^*$, which allows $\bar{z}(t)$ to be determined from $z(t)$.

Expressing the functional \mathcal{Y} of (6.8) in the auxiliary variables x, y, ξ, η , splitting the kinetic term and integrating by parts (as done for the free particle in Appendix B) and using the classical equations of motion (6.18a, b, c, d), one obtains:

$$\mathcal{Y}[x, \xi, y, \eta] = \frac{M}{2} \left[\dot{x}\xi + \dot{y}\eta + \dot{\xi}x + \dot{\eta}y \right]_a^b - \frac{M\gamma w}{2} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt [x_a \xi(t) + y_a \eta(t)] e^{-w(t-t_a)} \quad (6.14)$$

The expression in square brackets in the integral is nothing other than $\dots = \text{Re}\{z_a^* \dot{\zeta}(t)\}$. It is convenient to split this term as $[\dots] = (1 - \theta)[\dots] + \theta[\dots]$ and in the first term substitute $\zeta(t)$ as derived from the classical equation of motion, equation (6.13a), in terms of $\ddot{\zeta}$ and $\dot{\zeta}$. Integrating the term with $\ddot{\zeta}$ by parts and

rearranging the whole expression, one finds that if $\theta = \omega_B/\gamma$ the functional \mathcal{Y} simplifies to:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Y}[x, \xi, y, \eta] = & \frac{M}{2} \left[-\dot{x}_b \xi_b + \dot{x}_a \xi_a - \dot{y}_b \eta_b + \dot{y}_a \eta_a - \dot{\xi}_b (x_b - x_a) - \dot{\eta}_b (y_b - y_a) \right] \\ & + \frac{M\omega_B}{2} [y_a (\xi_b - \xi_a) - x_a (\eta_b - \eta_a)] \end{aligned} \quad (6.15)$$

Here too, to compute \mathcal{Y} it is not necessary to use the complete solutions of the classical equations $x(t)$, $y(t)$, $\xi(t)$, $\eta(t)$. If one is interested only in the probability density $p(x_b, y_b, t_b)$, it suffices to compute the initial velocities \dot{x}_a and \dot{y}_a of the variables x and y and the final velocities $\dot{\xi}_b$ and $\dot{\eta}_b$ of the variables ξ and η .

Integrating equations (6.13a, b, c), they turn out to be linear functions of the variables x , y , ξ and η at the initial and final instants:

$$\dot{\zeta}_b \Big|_{\xi_b=\eta_b=0} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \beta \zeta_a \quad (6.16a)$$

$$\dot{z}_a \Big|_{\xi_b=\eta_b=0} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \alpha (z_b - z_a) - i\varepsilon \zeta_a \quad (6.16b)$$

$$\dot{\bar{z}}_a \Big|_{\xi_b=\eta_b=0} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \alpha (\bar{z}_b - \bar{z}_a) - i\varepsilon \zeta_a^* \quad (6.16c)$$

where α , β and ε are constants (α and β complex, ε real). Using the inverse formulae (6.12b) one obtains:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\xi}_b \Big|_{\xi_b=\eta_b=0} = \beta_R \xi_a - \beta_I \eta_a \\ \dot{\eta}_b \Big|_{\xi_b=\eta_b=0} = \beta_R \eta_a + \beta_I \xi_a \end{cases} \quad (6.17)$$

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_a \Big|_{\xi_b=\eta_b=0} = \alpha_R (x_b - x_a) - \alpha_I (y_b - y_a) - i\varepsilon \xi_a \\ \dot{y}_a \Big|_{\xi_b=\eta_b=0} = \alpha_I (x_b - x_a) + \alpha_R (y_b - y_a) - i\varepsilon \eta_a \end{cases} \quad (6.18)$$

where $\alpha_R = \text{Re}\{\alpha\}$, $\alpha_I = \text{Im}\{\alpha\}$, $\beta_R = \text{Re}\{\beta\}$, $\beta_I = \text{Im}\{\beta\}$. They depend on the type of noise considered and will be specified later for convenience.

Substituting the expressions found into (6.15) one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_e(x_b, 0, y_b, 0, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, y_a, \eta_a, t_a) = F(\tau) \exp \left\{ \frac{iM}{2\hbar} \left(2\xi_a [\alpha_R(x_b - x_o) - \alpha_I(y_b - y_o)] \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + 2\eta_a [\alpha_I(x_b - x_o) + \alpha_R(y_b - y_o)] \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - 2(x_a - x_o) [\alpha_R \xi_a + (\alpha_I - \frac{\omega_B}{2}) \eta_a] \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - 2(y_a - y_o) [\alpha_R \eta_a - (\alpha_I - \frac{\omega_B}{2}) \xi_a] - i\varepsilon(\xi_a^2 + \eta_a^2) \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6.19)$$

where $F(\tau)$ is a normalisation factor.

With the effective propagator of the reduced density matrix it is now possible to evolve a generic initial density matrix $\varrho(x_a, \xi_a, y_a, \eta_a, t_a)$ corresponding to a Gaussian wave packet $\psi_a(x_a, y_a, t_a)$ with given mean values of position and initial velocity. This can be obtained by multiplying two one-dimensional Gaussian packets, one in the variable x_a and one in the variable y_a :

$$\psi(x_a, y_a, t_a) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_o^2}} \exp \left(-\frac{(x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2}{4\sigma_o^2} + iK_x x_a + iK_y y_a \right) \quad (6.20)$$

where $x_o = \langle x(t_a) \rangle$ and $y_o = \langle y(t_a) \rangle$. However, $\hbar K_x/M$ and $\hbar K_y/M$ cannot be interpreted as the mean values of the velocity components $\hbar k_x/M$ and $\hbar k_y/M$ at the instant $t = t_a$.

Indeed $\hbar K_x$ and $\hbar K_y$ represent the initial mean values of the canonical momenta $P_x = -i\hbar\partial/\partial x$ and $P_y = -i\hbar\partial/\partial y$, which are related to the kinetic momenta p_x and p_y by:

$$P_x = p_x - \frac{eA_x}{c} \quad (6.21a)$$

$$P_y = p_y - \frac{eA_y}{c} \quad (6.21b)$$

Then it follows that:

$$\hbar K_x = \hbar k_x - \frac{e\langle A_x \rangle}{c} \quad (6.22a)$$

$$\hbar K_y = \hbar k_y - \frac{e\langle A_y \rangle}{c} \quad (6.22b)$$

Nel caso particolare della (6.1) i parametri K_x e K_y possono esprimersi come:

$$\hbar K_x = \hbar k_x + \frac{ey_o}{2c} \quad (6.23a)$$

$$\hbar K_y = \hbar k_y - \frac{ex_o}{2c} \quad (6.23b)$$

Prendendo il prodotto $\psi(x_{1a}, y_{1a}, t_a)\psi^*(x_{2a}, y_{2a}, t_a)$ e tenendo conto delle relations (6.23a, b) one obtains the desired density matrix:

$$\varrho(x_a, \xi_a, y_a, \eta_a, t_a) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_o^2} \exp\left\{ -\frac{(x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2}{2\sigma_o^2} - \frac{\xi_a^2 + \eta_a^2}{8\sigma_o^2} - i\left(k_x + \frac{ey_o}{2\hbar c}\right)\xi_a - i\left(k_y - \frac{ex_o}{2\hbar c}\right)\eta_a \right\} \quad (6.24)$$

where: $x_o = \langle x(t_a) \rangle$, $y_o = \langle y(t_a) \rangle$, $\hbar k_x/M = \langle \dot{x}(t_a) \rangle$, $\hbar k_y/M = \langle \dot{y}(t_a) \rangle$ (equazione (5.25) nel testo originale).

From which the following probability density is derived:

$$\begin{aligned} p(x_b, y_b, t_b) &= \varrho_b(x_b, 0, y_b, 0, t_b) \\ &= \int dx_a d\xi_a \int dy_a d\eta_a \mathcal{K}_e(x_b, 0, y_b, 0, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, y_a, \eta_a, t_a) \varrho(x_a, \xi_a, y_a, \eta_a, t_a) \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2(\tau)} \exp\left\{ -\frac{[x_b - x_m(\tau)]^2 + [y_b - y_m(\tau)]^2}{2\sigma(\tau)^2} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6.26)$$

which has the desired form, with:

$$x_m(\tau) = x_o + \frac{\alpha_R(\tau)\frac{\hbar k_x}{M} + \alpha_I(\tau)\frac{\hbar k_y}{M}}{|\alpha|^2} \quad (6.27a)$$

$$y_m(t) = y_o + \frac{\alpha_R(\tau)\frac{\hbar k_y}{M} - \alpha_I(\tau)\frac{\hbar k_x}{M}}{|\alpha|^2} \quad (6.27b)$$

$$\sigma_B^2(t) = \sigma_o^2 \left[1 + \frac{\omega_B^2}{4|\alpha|^2} - \frac{\alpha_I(\tau)\omega_B}{|\alpha|^2} + \left(\frac{\hbar}{2M\sigma_o^2|\alpha|} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{\hbar\varepsilon(\tau)}{M|\alpha|^2} \quad (6.27c)$$

The form of the functions $x_m(\tau)$, $y_m(\tau)$, $\sigma_B^2(\tau)$ depends on the type of noise.

White noise. Consider first the white noise limit. For $w \rightarrow \infty$ equations (6.13a,

b, c) reduce to:

$$\ddot{\zeta}(t) - (\gamma - i\omega_B)\dot{\zeta}(t) = 0 \quad (6.28a)$$

$$\ddot{z}(t) + (\gamma + i\omega_B)\dot{z}(t) = -if_o \quad (6.28b)$$

$$\ddot{\bar{z}}(t) + (\gamma - i\omega_B)\dot{\bar{z}}(t) = -if_o^* \quad (6.28c)$$

which once integrated give the following values for the above constants:

$$\alpha = -\beta^* = \frac{\gamma + i\omega_B}{1 - e^{-(\gamma+i\omega_B)\tau}} \longrightarrow \begin{cases} \alpha_R = \frac{\gamma[1 - e^{-\gamma\tau} \cos(\omega_B\tau)] + \omega_B e^{-\gamma\tau} \sin(\omega_B\tau)}{1 - 2e^{-\gamma\tau} \cos(\omega_B\tau) + e^{-2\gamma\tau}} \\ \alpha_I = \frac{\omega_B[1 - e^{-\gamma\tau} \cos(\omega_B\tau)] - \gamma e^{-\gamma\tau} \sin(\omega_B\tau)}{1 - 2e^{-\gamma\tau} \cos(\omega_B\tau) + e^{-2\gamma\tau}} \end{cases} \quad (6.29a)$$

$$|\alpha|^2 = \frac{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2}{1 + e^{-2\gamma\tau} - 2e^{-\gamma\tau} \cos(\omega_B\tau)} \quad (6.29b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon &= \frac{1}{\hbar\beta} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} ds \left| \frac{1 - e^{-(\gamma+i\omega_B)(t_b-s)}}{1 - e^{-(\gamma+i\omega_B)\tau}} \right|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{\hbar\beta} \cdot \frac{\tau - \frac{2e^{-\gamma\tau}}{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2} [\gamma \cos(\omega_B\tau) - \omega_B \sin(\omega_B\tau)] + \frac{1 - e^{-2\gamma\tau}}{2\gamma}}{1 - 2e^{-\gamma\tau} \cos(\omega_B\tau) + e^{-2\gamma\tau}} \end{aligned} \quad (6.29c)$$

Substituting these values into (6.27a, b) and denoting for brevity $\hbar k_x/M$ and $\hbar k_y/M$ by \dot{x}_o and \dot{y}_o respectively, one finds that the centre-of-mass motion follows the trajectory defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} x_m(\tau) &= x_o + \frac{\dot{x}_o\gamma + \dot{y}_o\omega_B}{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2} \\ &+ e^{-\gamma\tau} \left\{ \frac{\dot{x}_o}{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2} (-\gamma \cos(\omega_B\tau) + \omega_B \sin(\omega_B\tau)) - \frac{\dot{y}_o}{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2} (\omega_B \cos(\omega_B\tau) + \gamma \sin(\omega_B\tau)) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6.30a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_m(\tau) &= y_o + \frac{\dot{y}_o\gamma - \dot{x}_o\omega_B}{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2} \\ &+ e^{-\gamma\tau} \left\{ \frac{\dot{y}_o}{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2} (-\gamma \cos(\omega_B\tau) + \omega_B \sin(\omega_B\tau)) + \frac{\dot{x}_o}{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2} (\omega_B \cos(\omega_B\tau) + \gamma \sin(\omega_B\tau)) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6.30b)$$

which are precisely the solutions of the corresponding macroscopic problem:

$$\ddot{x}_m(\tau) + \gamma\dot{x}_m(\tau) - \omega_B\dot{y}_m(\tau) = 0 \quad (6.31a)$$

$$\ddot{y}_m(\tau) + \gamma\dot{y}_m(\tau) + \omega_B\dot{x}_m(\tau) = 0 \quad (6.31b)$$

with initial conditions $x(0) = x_o$, $y(0) = y_o$, $\dot{x}(0) = \dot{x}_o$, $\dot{y}(0) = \dot{y}_o$. The Gaussian packet thus moves precisely along the classical trajectory given by (6.30a, b).

In order to simplify the formulae it is useful to define the following quantities:

$$\dot{r}_o = \sqrt{\dot{x}_o^2 + \dot{y}_o^2}, \quad \sin \phi_o = \frac{\dot{y}_o}{\dot{r}_o}, \quad \cos \phi_o = \frac{\dot{x}_o}{\dot{r}_o} \quad (6.32a)$$

$$\gamma_B = \sqrt{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2}, \quad \sin \phi_B = \frac{\gamma}{\gamma_B}, \quad \cos \phi_B = \frac{\omega_B}{\gamma_B} \quad (6.32b)$$

The quantities \dot{r}_o and ϕ_o simply give the magnitude and direction of the initial mean velocity.

The meaning of the parameters γ_B and ϕ_B becomes clear when they are used to rewrite formulae (6.30a, b):

$$x_m(\tau) = x_o + \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B} [\sin(\phi_o + \phi_B) + e^{-\gamma\tau} \sin(\omega_B\tau - \phi_B - \phi_o)] \quad (6.33a)$$

$$y_m(\tau) = y_o + \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B} [-\cos(\phi_o + \phi_B) + e^{-\gamma\tau} \cos(\omega_B\tau - \phi_B - \phi_o)] \quad (6.33b)$$

For $\tau \rightarrow \infty$ the particle reaches the asymptotic point of the trajectory with coordinates:

$$x(\infty) = x_o + (\dot{r}_o/\gamma_B) \sin(\phi_o + \phi_B) \quad e \quad y(\infty) = y_o - (\dot{r}_o/\gamma_B) \cos(\phi_o + \phi_B) \quad (6.34)$$

The angle $\pi/2 - \phi_B$ is therefore the one between the direction of the initial velocity and that of the vector (applied at the initial point) identifying the asymptotic point.

The maximum distance Δr travelled by the particle is:

$$\Delta r = \sqrt{[x(\infty) - x_o]^2 + [y(\infty) - y_o]^2} = \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B} \quad (6.35a)$$

$$\text{where: } \gamma_B = \sqrt{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2} \quad (6.35b)$$

which is to be compared with the analogous expression $\Delta x = \dot{x}_o/\gamma$ of the one-dimensional case, equation (1.41).

The parameter γ_B acts as an “effective damping coefficient” and since $\gamma_B \geq \gamma$ one can say that the average effect of the magnetic field is always that of increasing the damping.

If one also computes the distance $R(\tau)$ between the position of the particle and the asymptotic point of the trajectory (6.34a, b), one obtains:

$$R(\tau) = \sqrt{[x(\tau) - x(\infty)]^2 + [y(\tau) - y(\infty)]^2} = \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B} e^{-\gamma\tau} \quad (6.36)$$

which shows that the particle approaches the asymptotic point along an exponential spiral.

As regards the variance $\sigma_B^2(\tau)$, using the formulae for $\alpha_R(\tau)$, $\alpha_I(\tau)$, $\varepsilon(\tau)$ given in (6.29a, b, c), the asymptotic limit for $\gamma\tau \gg 1$ is:

$$\sigma_B^2(\gamma\tau \gg 1) = \sigma_o^2 \left[\frac{1 + (\omega_B/2\gamma)^2 + (\hbar/2M\sigma_o^2|\alpha|)^2}{1 + (\omega_B/\gamma)^2} \right] + \frac{2\gamma\tau}{M\beta(\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2)} \quad (6.37)$$

Comparing this expression with that of the free particle in the absence of a magnetic field, one observes that for $\omega_B = 0$, σ_B^2 reduces to the free case. Furthermore the effect of the magnetic field is to reduce the variance, i.e. to favour localisation of the wave packet: it is easy to show that for every value of B equation (6.37) is always less than the corresponding equation evaluated for $B = 0$.

The last term is formally diffusive ($\propto \tau$). It can be written in the form $2D_B\tau$ by replacing the damping coefficient γ with the effective damping coefficient $\Gamma_B = (\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2)/\gamma$ in Einstein's relation for the diffusion coefficient:

$$D_B = \frac{1}{M\beta\Gamma_B} \quad (6.38a)$$

$$\text{where: } \Gamma_B = \frac{\gamma^2 + \omega_B^2}{\gamma} \quad (6.38b)$$

The root-mean-square displacement follows practically the classical law $\Delta r(\tau)^2 \simeq \Delta r(0)^2 + 2D_B\tau$, and the particle diffuses through space with a probability density $p(x, y, z, t)$ which, within the limits of validity of the diffusion equation, satisfies:

$$\frac{\partial p(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} = D_B \left(\frac{\partial^2 p(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y^2} \right) + D \frac{\partial^2 p(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z^2} \quad (6.39)$$

Following a more rigorous procedure (by taking the classical limit from the density matrix equation), it can be shown that one arrives at the corresponding Kramers equation [43].

By applying sufficiently strong magnetic fields one can make the damping coefficient Γ_B arbitrarily large, and hence the diffusion coefficient D_B arbitrarily small. This effect of the magnetic field on diffusion should be detectable, for example, by studying the diffusion of an electrolyte solution in the directions parallel and perpendicular to an applied magnetic field.

Lorentzian noise. The problem of a particle moving in a constant magnetic field in a dissipative environment with Lorentzian noise is, beyond the novelty of the application, of particular interest due to oscillations appearing in time both in the variance $\sigma_B^2(\tau)$ and in the mean position $(x_m(\tau), y_m(\tau))$ of the wave packet.

The effect is of classical origin, in the sense that it is already present in the solution of the classical equations of motion.

The frequency of these “anomalous oscillations” depends in an essential way, in addition to the cyclotron frequency ω_B , on the cut-off frequency w and the damping constant γ , which are the two time scales characterising in general the effect of the environment on the system in the case of Lorentzian noise.

The effect disappears, however, in the case of white noise, treated in the preceding section.

The calculations proceed in a perfectly analogous way to those of the white noise case.

With the method used in Chapter 1, it is possible to reduce equations (6.13a, b, c) to second-order linear equations for harmonic oscillators:

$$\ddot{\zeta}(t) - (w - i\omega_B)\dot{\zeta}(t) + w(\gamma - i\omega_B)\zeta(t) = -w\dot{\zeta}_b - i\omega_B w\zeta_B \quad (6.40a)$$

$$\ddot{z}(t) + (w + i\omega_B)\dot{z}(t) + w(\gamma + i\omega_B)z(t) = w(\gamma + i\omega_B)z_a + w\dot{z}_a - if_o \quad (6.40b)$$

$$\ddot{\bar{z}}(t) + (w - i\omega_B)\dot{\bar{z}}(t) + w(\gamma - i\omega_B)\bar{z}(t) = w(\gamma - i\omega_B)\bar{z}_a + w\dot{\bar{z}}_a - if_o^* \quad (6.40c)$$

One can obtain the solution by first solving the equation for ζ , which is that of a damped harmonic oscillator, and then, given ζ and hence $f_o[\zeta]$, deriving $z(t)$ and $\bar{z}(t)$. Given ζ , z and \bar{z} , the constants α , β and ε can finally be computed.

The result in this case too is equation (6.26) with the functions $x_m(\tau)$ and $y_m(\tau)$ coinciding with the solutions of the corresponding macroscopic problem.

While in the white noise case the oscillation frequency was unique and coincided with the cyclotron frequency ω_B , the time behaviour now depends on two frequencies Ω_1 and Ω_2 . To see how this arises, consider the macroscopic equations

$$\ddot{z}(\tau) + (w + i\omega_B)\dot{z}(\tau) + w(\gamma + i\omega_B)z(\tau) = w(\gamma + i\omega_B)z_o + w\dot{z}_o \quad (6.41)$$

where $z(\tau) = x_m(\tau) + iy_m(\tau)$.

This is the problem of a damped harmonic oscillator (with a driving term depending on the initial conditions z_o , y_o and \dot{x}_o , \dot{y}_o). Seeking a solution of the form $z \propto e^{-\Omega\tau}$ one obtains the second-degree equation with complex coefficients:

$$\Omega^2 - (w + i\omega_B)\Omega + w(\gamma + i\omega_B) = 0 \quad (6.42)$$

$$\text{from which: } \Omega_{1,2} = \frac{w + i\omega_B}{2} + \left[\left(\frac{w^2}{4} - \frac{\omega_B^2}{4} - w\gamma \right) - \frac{iw\omega_B}{2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (6.43)$$

The two solutions $\Omega_{1,2}$ can be determined using the formula giving the square

roots of a complex number in terms of its real and imaginary parts. If A and B are two real numbers:

$$[A + iB]^{1/2} = \pm \left[\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{A^2 + B^2} + A)} + i \operatorname{sgn}(B) \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{A^2 + B^2} - A)} \right] \quad (6.44)$$

from which the two frequencies $\Omega_{1,2}$ are:

$$\Omega_1 = \frac{w + \delta_1}{2} + i \frac{\omega_B - \delta_2}{2} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \gamma^+ + i\Omega^- \quad (6.45a)$$

$$\Omega_2 = \frac{w - \delta_1}{2} + i \frac{\omega_B + \delta_2}{2} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \gamma^- + i\Omega^+ \quad (6.45b)$$

where the following have been defined:

$$\frac{\delta_1}{2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\sqrt{\left(\frac{w^2}{4} - \frac{\omega_B^2}{4} - w\gamma\right)^2 + \left(\frac{w\omega_B}{2}\right)^2} + \frac{w^2}{4} - \frac{\omega_B^2}{4} - w\gamma} \quad (6.46a)$$

$$\frac{\delta_2}{2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\sqrt{\left(\frac{w^2}{4} - \frac{\omega_B^2}{4} - w\gamma\right)^2 + \left(\frac{w\omega_B}{2}\right)^2} - \frac{w^2}{4} + \frac{\omega_B^2}{4} + w\gamma} \quad (6.46b)$$

$$\gamma^\pm = w \pm \delta_1 \quad (6.46c)$$

$$\Omega^\pm = \omega_B \pm \delta_2 \quad (6.46d)$$

The parameters γ^\pm and Ω^\pm allow one to define further parameters Γ^\pm and ϕ^\pm , analogous to those introduced for white noise, with which the formulae can be considerably simplified:

$$\Gamma^+ = \sqrt{(\Omega^+)^2 + (\gamma - \gamma^+)^2}, \quad \cos \phi^+ = \frac{\Omega^+}{\Gamma^+}, \quad \sin \phi^+ = \frac{\gamma - \gamma^+}{\Gamma^+} \quad (6.47a)$$

$$\Gamma^- = \sqrt{(\Omega^-)^2 + (\gamma - \gamma^-)^2}, \quad \cos \phi^- = \frac{\Omega^-}{\Gamma^-}, \quad \sin \phi^- = \frac{\gamma - \gamma^-}{\Gamma^-} \quad (6.47b)$$

With the new parameters the macroscopic solutions take the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_m(\tau) &= x_o + \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B} \sin(\phi_o + \phi_B) \\
&+ \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B(\delta_1 - \delta_2)} \left[\Gamma^+ e^{-\tau\Gamma^-} \cos(\tau\Omega^+ + \phi^+ - \phi_B - \phi_o) + \Gamma^- e^{-\tau\Gamma^+} \cos(\tau\Omega^- - \phi^- + \phi_B + \phi_o) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{6.48a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_m(\tau) &= y_o - \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B} \cos(\phi_o + \phi_B) \\
&- \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B(\delta_1 - \delta_2)} \left[\Gamma^+ e^{-\tau\Gamma^-} \sin(\tau\Omega^+ + \phi^+ - \phi_B - \phi_o) + \Gamma^- e^{-\tau\Gamma^+} \sin(\tau\Omega^- - \phi^- + \phi_B + \phi_o) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{6.48b}$$

One sees that, in analogy with the case without a magnetic field, the asymptotic limits for $\tau \rightarrow \infty$ are the same for white noise and for Lorentzian noise. In particular the distance travelled is again $\Delta r = \dot{r}_o/\gamma_B$.

The trajectory along which the particle approaches the asymptotic point is however different, because damped oscillations are present.

To highlight them one can compute the distance $R(\tau)$ between the position of the particle at time τ and the asymptotic position. While in the white noise case $R(\tau)$ traced an exponential spiral as τ varied, equation (6.36), one now has, recalling that $\Omega^+ - \Omega^- = \delta_2$:

$$\begin{aligned}
R(\tau) &= \sqrt{[x_c(\tau) - x_c(\infty)]^2 + [y_c(\tau) - y_c(\infty)]^2} \\
&= \frac{\dot{r}_o}{\gamma_B(\delta_1 - \delta_2)} \sqrt{(\Gamma^+)^2 e^{-2\tau\Gamma^-} + (\Gamma^-)^2 e^{-2\tau\Gamma^+} + 2\Gamma^+\Gamma^- e^{-\tau(\Gamma^- + \Gamma^+)} \cos(\delta_2\tau + \phi)}
\end{aligned} \tag{6.49}$$

where $\phi = \phi^+ - \phi^- + 2(\phi_B + \phi_o)$. The oscillations are characterised by a decay time $\tau \simeq 1/(\Gamma^- + \Gamma^+)$ and a frequency $\delta_2/2\pi$. Since $\delta_2 \rightarrow 0$ for $w \rightarrow \infty$, they disappear in the white noise limit.

The same type of oscillations characterises the time behaviour of $\sigma(\tau)$.

Surviving for a mean time of order γ^{-1} , these oscillations should be directly observable.

Appendix A: Calculation of the influence functional

Recall the formula for the effective propagator \mathcal{K}_e for the reduced density matrix of the central particle:

$$\mathcal{K}_e(x_{1b}, x_{2b}, t_b | x_{1a}, x_{2a}, t_a) = \int_{x_{1a}}^{x_{1b}} \mathcal{D}x_1 \int_{x_{2a}}^{x_{2b}} \mathcal{D}x_2 \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar}[S_o[x_1] - S_o[x_2]]\right\} \mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2] \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where the influence functional \mathcal{F} is:

$$\mathcal{F}[x_1, x_2] = \int dq_b \int dq_{1a} dq_{2a} K^*(q_b, t_b | q_{2a}, t_a; [x_2]) K(q_b, t_b | q_{1a}, t_a; [x_1]) \varrho_q(q_{1a}, q_{2a}, x_{1a}, x_{2a}; \beta) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where the propagator of the forced harmonic oscillator $K(q_b, t_b | q_a, t_a; [f])$ is given explicitly in (2.21), and the initial density matrix of the oscillator is $\varrho_q(q_{1a}, q_{2a}, x_{1a}, x_{2a}; \beta) = \varrho_\beta(q_{1a} - x_a, q_{2a} - x_a)$ with $x_a = (x_{1a} + x_{2a})/2$, the form of the matrix $\varrho_\beta(q_1, q_2)$ being that of the harmonic oscillator given in (2.8).

Passing to the variables (the corresponding Jacobian is unity):

$$x = \frac{x_1 + x_2}{2}, \quad \xi = x_2 - x_1, \quad q_a = \frac{q_{1a} + q_{2a}}{2}, \quad \chi_a = q_{2a} - q_{1a} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

we have that:

$$1) \int dq_{1a} dq_{2a} (\dots) = \int dq_a d\xi_a (\dots) \quad (\text{A.4a})$$

$$2) \varrho_q(q_a - x_a, \chi_a; \beta) = \varrho_\beta(q_{1a} - x_a, q_{2a} - x_a) = \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar \coth(\beta\hbar\omega/2)}} \exp\left\{-\frac{m\omega}{\hbar} \left((q_a - x_a)^2 \text{th}\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right) + \frac{\chi_a^2}{4} \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right) \right)\right\} \quad (\text{A.4b})$$

$$3) K^*(q_b, t_b | q_{2a}, t_a; [x_2]) K(q_b, t_b | q_{1a}, t_a; [x_1]) = \frac{m\omega}{2\pi\hbar \sin(\omega\tau)} \times \exp\left\{\frac{im\omega}{2\hbar \sin(\omega\tau)} [-2q_a\chi_a \cos(\omega\tau) + 2\chi_a(q_b - f[x]) - 2q_a g[\xi] - 2q_b l[\xi] + 2H[x, \xi]]\right\} \quad (\text{A.4c})$$

where the functionals f , g and H have been defined in the following way:

$$f[x] = \omega \int_{t_a}^{t_b} ds x(s) \sin[\omega(t_b - s)] g[x] = \omega \int_{t_a}^{t_b} ds x(s) \sin[\omega(s - t_a)] \quad (\text{A.5ab})$$

$$H[x, \xi] = \omega \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds [x(t)\xi(s) + x(s)\xi(t)] \sin[\omega(t_b - t)] \sin[\omega(s - t_a)] \quad (\text{A.5c})$$

Substituting items 1), 2) and 3) into (A.2), the integration over q_a and χ_a can be performed with the help of the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int dx dy \exp[-Ax^2 - By^2 + 2Cxy + Dx + Ey] \\ &= \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{AB - C^2}} \exp\left\{ \frac{AE^2 + 2CDE + BD^2}{4(AB - C^2)} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

obtaining the following expression for the influence functional:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}[x, \xi] &= F(\tau) \int dq_b \exp\left\{ -\frac{m\omega}{\hbar} \left[\frac{i}{\sin(\omega\tau)} (g[\xi] + f[\xi] \cos(\omega\tau)) q_b + \text{th}\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right) (q'_b)^2 \right] \right\} \\ &\times \exp\left\{ -\frac{m\omega}{\hbar} \left[\frac{i(g[\xi]f[x] - H[x, \xi])}{\sin(\omega\tau)} + \frac{ix_a(g[\xi] \cos(\omega\tau) + f[\xi])}{\sin(\omega\tau)} + \frac{1}{4} f^2[\xi] \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right) \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where $q'_b = q_b - f[x] - x_a \cos(\omega\tau)$ and $F(\tau)$ is given by:

$$F(\tau) = \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar \coth(\beta\hbar\omega/2)}} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Defining new functionals through the relations:

$$g[\xi] + f[\xi] \cos(\omega\tau) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sin(\omega\tau) h[\xi] = \sin(\omega\tau) \omega \int_{t_a}^{t_b} ds \xi(s) \cos[\omega(t_b - s)] \quad (\text{A.9a})$$

$$g[\xi] \cos(\omega\tau) + f[\xi] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sin(\omega\tau) l[\xi] = \sin(\omega\tau) \omega \int_{t_a}^{t_b} ds \xi(s) \cos[\omega(s - t_a)] \quad (\text{A.9b})$$

and noting that:

$$g[\xi]f[x] - H[x, \xi] = \sin(\omega\tau) \omega^2 \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)x(s) \sin[\omega(t - s)] \quad (\text{A.9c})$$

the last integration can be readily performed to obtain finally:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}[x, \xi] = \exp \left\{ -\frac{m\omega}{\hbar} \left(ix_a \omega \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \xi(t) \cos[\omega(t - t_a)] \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + i\omega^2 \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)x(s) \sin[\omega(t - s)] \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right) \omega^2 \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)\xi(s) \cos[\omega(t - s)] \right) \right\} \quad (\text{A.10}) \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the expression found into (A.1), the effective propagator is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_e(x_b, \xi_b, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) = \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \mathcal{D}x \int_{\xi_a}^{\xi_b} \mathcal{D}\xi \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left(-M\dot{x}\dot{\xi} + V(x + \xi/2) - V(x - \xi/2) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + m\omega^2[x(t) - x_a]\xi(t) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - M\omega^3 \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)[x(s) - x_a] \sin[\omega(t - s)] \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \frac{i}{2} \coth\left(\frac{\beta\hbar\omega}{2}\right) m\omega^3 \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)\xi(s) \cos[\omega(t - s)] \right) \right\} \quad (\text{A.11}) \end{aligned}$$

Returning to the original variables x_1 and x_2 , one obtains the formulae (2.24) and (2.26) for the effective propagator.

Summing the contributions from all oscillators one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_e(x_b, \xi_b, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) \\ = \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \mathcal{D}x \int_{\xi_a}^{\xi_b} \mathcal{D}\xi \exp \left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left(-M\dot{x}\dot{\xi} + V(x + \xi/2) - V(x - \xi/2) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + k_e[x(t) - x_a]\xi(t) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)[x(s) - x_a]\alpha_1(t - s) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + i \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)\xi(s)\alpha_2(t - s) \right) \right\} \quad (\text{A.12}) \end{aligned}$$

Appendix B: Effective propagator for the free particle

In this appendix the propagator of the density matrix of the central particle for a free particle in a dissipative environment with white or Lorentzian noise is computed.

In the case $V = 0$ (free particle) the effective propagator \mathcal{K}_e is a quadratic functional of the trajectories x and ξ :

$$\mathcal{K}_e(x_b, \xi_b, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) = \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \mathcal{D}x \int_{\xi_a}^{\xi_b} \mathcal{D}\xi \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{Y}[x, \xi]\right\} \quad (\text{B.1a})$$

con:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Y}[x, \xi] = & \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \mathcal{D}x \int_{\xi_a}^{\xi_b} \mathcal{D}\xi \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \left(-M\dot{x}\dot{\xi} + m\omega^2[x(t) - x_a]\xi(t)\right.\right. \\ & \left.\left. - \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)\alpha_1(t-s)[x(s) - x_a] + i \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \int_{t_a}^t ds \xi(t)\alpha_2(t-s)\xi(s)\right)\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.1b})$$

and can be computed according to the formula:

$$\mathcal{K}_e(x_b, \xi_b, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) = F(\tau) \exp\left\{\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{Y}_{cl}[x, \xi]\right\} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where $F(\tau)$ is a factor determinable by normalisation conditions and $\mathcal{Y}_{cl}[x, \xi] = \mathcal{Y}[x_{cl}, \xi_{cl}]$ is the classical functional, evaluated along the classical trajectories defined by the following equations, derived by setting $\delta\mathcal{Y}/\delta x(t) = 0$ and $\delta\mathcal{Y}/\delta\xi(t) = 0$:

$$\ddot{\xi}(t) + \gamma w \xi(t) + \gamma w^2 \int_t^{t_b} ds \xi(s) e^{-w(s-t)} = 0 \quad (\text{B.3a})$$

$$\ddot{x}(t) + \gamma w [x(t) - x_a] + \gamma w^2 \int_{t_a}^t ds [x(s) - x_a] e^{-w(s-t)} + i f_o(t) = 0 \quad (\text{B.3b})$$

where:

$$f_o(t) = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} ds \alpha_R(|t-s|)\xi(s) \quad (\text{B.3c})$$

The function f_o represents, for x , an external force whose form is in principle known once the equation for $\xi(t)$ has been solved. In practice, since the function α_R does not permit exact integration except in particular limits, f_o cannot in general be written explicitly but only its asymptotic behaviour ($t \rightarrow \infty$) can be deduced.

It is nevertheless possible to draw some general conclusions based solely on the fact that the contribution of f_o to the equation for x is imaginary.

As with any quadratic action, the computation of the classical action can be simplified by the following procedure.

Split the kinetic term into two equal parts, $-M\dot{x}\dot{\xi} \rightarrow -\frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}\dot{\xi} - \frac{1}{2}M\dot{x}\dot{\xi}$, and integrate the first by parts with respect to $dx = \dot{x} dt$ and the second with respect to $d\xi = \dot{\xi} dt$.

Using the classical equations of motion (B.3a, b) one obtains:

$$\mathcal{Y}_{cl} = \frac{M}{2} [x_a \dot{\xi}_a + \dot{x}_a \xi_a - x_b \dot{\xi}_b - \dot{x}_b \xi_b] - \frac{x_a}{2} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \xi(t) \sum_n m\omega_n^2 \cos[\omega_n(t - t_a)] \quad (\text{B.4})$$

The function in the integral is proportional to the correlation function $u(t - s)$. For Lorentzian noise, see (1.29), $\sum_n m\omega_n^2 \cos(\omega_n \tau) = M\gamma w e^{-w\tau}$. Substituting this expression into the integral and also substituting $\xi(t)$ with the expression derived from its equation of motion in terms of $\dot{\xi}$ and $\ddot{\xi}$, after integrating by parts the term with $\ddot{\xi}(t)$ one obtains:

$$\mathcal{Y}_{cl} = \frac{M}{2} [-(x_b - x_a)\dot{\xi}_b + \dot{x}_a \xi_a - \dot{x}_b \xi_b] \quad (\text{B.5})$$

This expression, besides being translationally invariant, is useful because it involves no integrals over the functions α_1 and α_2 , allowing one, without any of the risks mentioned above, to pass to the white noise limit simply by using for \dot{x}_a , \dot{x}_b and $\dot{\xi}_b$ the values computed from the corresponding classical equation.

One also sees that if one is interested only in computing the probability density $p(x_b, t_b) = \varrho(x_b, \xi_b = 0, t_b)$, it suffices to compute the two velocities \dot{x}_a and $\dot{\xi}_b$.

Since the white noise limit can always be obtained at the end by setting $\gamma/w \rightarrow \infty$, the case of Lorentzian noise will be studied directly.

To solve the equations of motion, introduce the following functionals:

$$f_1(t) = \gamma w^2 \int_{t_a}^t ds [x(s) - x_a] e^{-w(t-s)}, \quad f_2(t) = \gamma w^2 \int_t^{t_b} ds \xi(s) e^{-w(s-t)} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

with which the equations of motion (B.3a, b) rewrite as:

$$\ddot{\xi}(t) + \gamma w \xi(t) - f_2(t) = 0 \quad (\text{B.7a})$$

$$\ddot{x}(t) + \gamma w [x(t) - x_a] - f_1(t) + i f_o(t) = 0 \quad (\text{B.7b})$$

Differentiating f_1 and f_2 with respect to time, one obtains $\dot{f}_1(t) = \gamma w^2 [x(t) -$

$x_a] - wf_1(t)$ and $\dot{f}_2(t) = -\gamma w^2 \xi(t) + wf_2(t)$; from these f_1 and f_2 can be extracted and substituted back into (B.7a, b). Integrating in time from t_a to t and from t to t_b respectively for the resulting equations for $x(t)$ and $\xi(t)$, one obtains:

$$f_1(t) = -w[\dot{x}(t) - \dot{x}_a] - iw \int_{t_a}^t ds f_o(s) \quad (\text{B.8a})$$

$$f_2(t) = w[\dot{\xi}(t) - \dot{\xi}_b] \quad (\text{B.8b})$$

where $\dot{x}_a = \dot{x}(t_a)$ and $\dot{\xi}_b = \dot{\xi}(t_b)$; substituting back into (B.7a, b) one obtains a damped (forced) harmonic oscillator equation for x and an anti-damped oscillator equation for ξ :

$$\ddot{\xi}(t) - w[\dot{\xi}(t) - \dot{\xi}_b] + \gamma w \xi(t) = 0 \quad (\text{B.9a})$$

$$\ddot{x}(t) + w[\dot{x}(t) - \dot{x}_a] + \gamma w[x(t) - x_a] = -i\varphi_o(t) \quad (\text{B.9b})$$

where:

$$\varphi_o(t) = f_o(t) + w \int_{t_a}^t ds f_o(s) \quad (\text{B.9c})$$

Solving these equations and expressing the solutions $x(t)$ and $\xi(t)$ as functions of the values at the endpoints of the trajectory, x_a, x_b and ξ_a, ξ_b respectively, one can derive:

$$\dot{\xi}_b = \alpha \xi_a + \alpha' \xi_b \quad (\text{B.10a})$$

$$\dot{x}_a = -\alpha(x_b - x_a) + i\varepsilon \xi_a + i\varepsilon' \xi_b \quad (\text{B.10b})$$

$$\text{con: } \alpha = -\frac{\gamma}{\Delta(\tau)} \quad (\text{B.10c})$$

where the function $\Delta(\tau)$ is the same one appearing in the macroscopic solution (1.39) of a particle in a Lorentzian noise environment. The constant ε is more conveniently expressed as:

$$\xi(t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} C_a(t)\xi_a + C_b(t_b)\xi_b \quad (\text{B.11a})$$

$$f_a(t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} ds C_a(s) \alpha_R(|t-s|) \quad (\text{B.11b})$$

$$\varepsilon(\tau) = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt \exp\left[-\frac{w}{2}(t-t_a)\right] \frac{\text{sh}[\delta(t_b-t)]}{\text{sh}(\delta\tau)} f_a(t) \quad (\text{B.11c})$$

as can be verified by solving (B.9a, b, c) directly.

In view of computing the probability density (obtained by setting $\xi_b = 0$), using

(B.10a, b) in (B.5) one finally obtains:

$$\mathcal{K}_e(x_b, 0, t_b | x_a, \xi_a, t_a) = F(\tau) \exp\left(-\frac{iM\alpha}{\hbar}(x_b - x_a)\xi_a - \frac{M\varepsilon}{\hbar}\xi_a^2\right) \quad (\text{B.12})$$

Appendix C: Probability functional for Gaussian processes

Suppose that a stochastic process $\phi(t)$ is characterised by the following statistical properties:

$$\langle \phi(t) \rangle = 0 \quad (\text{C.1a})$$

$$\langle \phi(t)\phi(s) \rangle = \mathcal{C} \delta(t - s) \quad (\text{C.1b})$$

where \mathcal{C} is a positive constant, similar to those of the stochastic force of the Langevin equation. One seeks the corresponding probability functional $P[\phi]$, i.e. the functional such that (C.1a) and (C.1b) can be recovered by averaging over the ensemble of possible forms of the function $\phi(t)$:

$$\langle \phi(t) \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\phi P[\phi] \phi(t) = 0 \quad (\text{C.2a})$$

$$\langle \phi(t)\phi(s) \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\phi P[\phi] \phi(t)\phi(s) = \mathcal{C} \delta(t - s) \quad (\text{C.2b})$$

The functional sought is of Gaussian type and is given exactly by:

$$P[\phi] = \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2\mathcal{C}} \int dt \phi^2(t)\right\} \quad (\text{C.3})$$

To prove this, the generating functional $\mathfrak{P}[k]$ defined as follows is useful:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{P}[k] &= \int \mathcal{D}\phi P[\phi] \exp\left\{\int dt k(t)\phi(t)\right\} \\ &= \int \mathcal{D}\phi \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2\mathcal{C}} \int dt \phi^2(t) + \int dt k(t)\phi(t)\right\} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \int \mathcal{D}f \exp(S[\phi, k]) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.4})$$

which, as is easily verified, gives the mean value and correlation through:

$$\langle \phi(t) \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\phi P[\phi] \phi(t) = \left. \frac{\delta \mathfrak{P}[k]}{\delta k(t)} \right|_{k(t)=0} \quad (\text{C.5a})$$

$$\langle \phi(t)\phi(s) \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\phi P[\phi] \phi(t)\phi(s) = \left. \frac{\delta^2 \mathfrak{P}[k]}{\delta k(t) \delta k(s)} \right|_{k(t)=0} \quad (\text{C.5b})$$

Since the functional S defined in equation (4.12) is quadratic in ϕ , the generating functional can be computed exactly as $\mathfrak{P}[k] \propto \exp(S_d)$ where $S_d = S[\phi_d, k]$ is the

classical functional [35]. It is the functional S evaluated for $\phi = \phi_{cl}(t)$, where $\phi_{cl}(t)$ is defined by the equation obtained by varying $S[\phi, k]$ with respect to ϕ : $\delta S = 0$. The condition, from (4.12), gives:

$$\delta S[\phi] = \delta \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\mathcal{C}} \int dt \phi^2(t) + \int dt k(t)\phi(t) \right\} = \int dt \delta\phi(t) \left\{ -\frac{\phi(t)}{\mathcal{C}} + k(t) \right\} \quad (\text{C.6})$$

from which $\phi_{cl}(t) = \mathcal{C} k(t)$. Together with the normalisation condition $\langle 1 \rangle = 1$, one readily obtains:

$$\mathfrak{P}[k] = \exp \left\{ \frac{\mathcal{C}}{2} \int dt k^2(t) \right\} \quad (\text{C.7})$$

Using (C.5a, b), equations (C.2a, b) are easily obtained.

What changes if the mean value is not zero but is some function $f_o(t)$?

In this case one can write the stochastic process as $f(t) = f_o(t) + \phi(t)$, where $\phi(t)$ is a stochastic term satisfying all the relations given above. Substituting $\phi(t) = f(t) - f_o(t)$, one can derive the statistical properties of $f(t)$:

$$\langle f(t) \rangle = f_o(t) \quad (\text{C.8a})$$

$$\langle [f(t) - f_o(t)][f(s) - f_o(s)] \rangle = \mathcal{C} \delta(t - s) \quad (\text{C.8b})$$

as well as its probability functional:

$$P[f] = \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\mathcal{C}} \int dt [f(t) - f_o(t)]^2 \right\} \quad (\text{C.9})$$

Bibliography

Articles on quantum Brownian motion

- [1] I.R. Senitzky: *Physical Review* **119**, 670 (1960).
- [2] R.E. Turner: *Physica* **26**, 269 (1960).
- [3] R.R. Rubin: *Journal of Mathematical Physics* **1**, 309 (1960).
- [4] W.H. Wells: *Annals of Physics* **12**, 1 (1961).
- [5] I.R. Senitzky: *Physical Review* **124**, 642 (1961).
- [6] R.R. Rubin: *Journal of Mathematical Physics* **2**, 373 (1961).
- [7] D.K.C. MacDonald: *Physica* **28**, 409 (1962).
- [8] S. Takeno, J. Hori: *Suppl. Progr. Theoretical Physics* **23**, 177 (1962).
- [9] R.P. Feynman, F.L. Vernon: *Annals of Physics* **24**, 118 (1963).
- [10] P. Mazur, E. Braun: *Physica* **30**, 1973 (1964).
- [11] G.W. Ford, M. Kac, P. Mazur: *Journal of Mathematical Physics* **6**, 504 (1965).
- [12] P. Ullersma: *Physica* **32**, 27 (1966).
- [13] H. Dekker: *Physics Reports* **80**(1), 1 (1981).
- [14] A.O. Caldeira, A.J. Leggett: *Physica* **121 A**, 587 (1983).
- [15] K. Lindenberg, B. West: *Physical Review A* **30**, 568 (1984).
- [16] H. Grabert, U. Weiss, P. Talkner: *Zeitschrift für Physik B* **55**, 87 (1984).
- [17] V. Hakim, V. Ambegaokar: *Physical Review A* **32**, 423 (1985).
- [18] G.W. Ford, M. Kac: *Journal of Statistical Physics* **46**, 803 (1987).
- [19] W. Eckhardt: *Physica* **141A**, 81 (1987).
- [20] P. Schramm, H. Grabert: *Journal of Statistical Physics* **49**, 767 (1987).
- [21] H. Grabert, P. Schramm, G.L. Ingold: *Physics Reports* **168**(3), 115 (1988).

[22] C.M. Smith, A.O. Caldeira: *Physical Review A* **41**, 3103 (1990).

Articles on classical Brownian motion

[23] H. Mori: *Progr. Theor. Phys.*, Japan, **33**, 423 (1965).

[24] R. Kubo: *Reports on Progress in Physics* **29**, 255 (1966).

General texts

[25] L.D. Landau, E.M. Lifshits: § 52, Vol. 2, *Field Theory*, Editori Riuniti, 1981.

[26] *ibidem* § 16.

[27] L.D. Landau, E.M. Lifshits: § 14, Vol. 3, *Quantum Mechanics*, Editori Riuniti, 1982.

[28] L.D. Landau, E.M. Lifshits: § 2, Vol. 4, *Relativistic Quantum Theory*, Editori Riuniti, 1978.

[29] L.D. Landau, E.M. Lifshits: § 44, Vol. 5, *Statistical Physics*, Editori Riuniti, 1978.

[30] *ibidem* § 30.

[31] L.D. Landau, E.M. Lifshits: § 12, Vol. 10, *Kinetic Theory*, Editori Riuniti, 1984.

[32] *ibidem* § 3.

[33] R.P. Feynman, A.R. Hibbs: §§ 12-8/9, *Quantum Mechanics and Path Integrals*, McGraw-Hill, 1965.

[34] *ibidem* § 3-1.

[35] *ibidem* § 3-5.

[36] *ibidem* § 3-6.

[37] *ibidem* § 3-7.

[38] *ibidem* § 10-2.

[39] *ibidem* § 10.

- [40] *ibidem* § 12-4.
- [41] *Enciclopedia del Novecento*, Istituto della Enciclopedia Italiana, 1984, under the entry: “Stocastica”.
- [42] N.G. van Kampen: § VIII-8, *Stochastic Processes in Physics and Chemistry*, North-Holland.
- [43] *ibidem* § V-8.
- [44] *ibidem* § V.
- [45] R.P. Feynman: § 2, *Statistical Mechanics*, W.A. Benjamin, 1972.
- [46] H. Risken: *The Fokker-Planck Equation*, Springer-Verlag, 1984.
- [47] M. Toda, R. Kubo, V. Saito: *Statistical Physics*, Vol. II, Springer, 1983.
- [48] P.W. Atkins: § 27.3, *Physical Chemistry*, Oxford University Press, 1986.
- [49] *ibidem* Table (27.4).
- [50] *ibidem* § 27.2.
- [51] H. Goldstein: § 1-5, *Classical Mechanics*, Zanichelli, Bologna, 1971.
- [52] M. Jammer: *The Philosophy of Quantum Mechanics*, John Wiley & Sons, 1974.
- [53] See R.P. Feynman in: J. Schwinger ed., *Quantum Electrodynamics*, Dover, 1958.
- [54] L.I. Schiff: § 13, *Quantum Mechanics*, McGraw-Hill, Third Edition, 1968.
- [55] *ibidem* § 40.
- [56] C. Kittel: § 6, *Introduction to Solid State Physics*, Boringhieri, 1971.

Other articles

- [57] G. Jona-Lasinio, P. Claverie: *Progress of Theoretical Physics Supplement* No. 86, 54 (1986).
- [58] E. Schrödinger: *Naturwiss.*, **14**, 664 (1926).

Publications related to the thesis

The following articles were published after the defence of the thesis and are directly based on the work presented therein:

1. M. Patriarca, *Statistical correlations in the oscillator model of quantum dissipative systems*, *Il Nuovo Cimento B* **111**, 61 (1996).
[doi:10.1007/BF02726201](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02726201) [arXiv:1801.02429](https://arxiv.org/abs/1801.02429)
2. F. Illuminati, M. Patriarca, P. Sodano, *Quantum dissipation in non-homogeneous environments*, in: *Fluctuation Phenomena: Disorder and Nonlinearity*, A.R. Bishop, S. Jimenez, L. Vazquez (eds.), World Scientific, Singapore (1995), p. 53.
[doi:10.1142/9789814503877_0012](https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814503877_0012)
3. F. Illuminati, M. Patriarca, P. Sodano, *Classical and quantum dissipation in nonhomogeneous environments*, *Physica A* **211**, 449 (1994).
[doi:10.1016/0378-4371\(94\)00171-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4371(94)00171-5) [arXiv:hep-th/9406024](https://arxiv.org/abs/hep-th/9406024)

For an up-to-date list of the author's publications:

1. [ORCID](#)
2. [Google Scholar profile](#)